

WP3 – Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Concept and establishment of a biodiversity tool for agroforestry applications in Europe

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Executive Summary

Agroforestry is increasingly promoted as a nature-based solution to reconcile agricultural production with sustainability goals such as biodiversity conservation. Yet, to our knowledge there are no robust evidence-based decision-supporting tools to specifically quantify agroforestry implementation benefits on biodiversity in Europe. Hence in this report, we present the development of an evidence-based, data-driven biodiversity assessment tool specifically tailored to agroforestry systems.

We compiled a high-resolution database from existing agroforestry case-studies. These case-studies were selected among existing meta-analyses, a systematic review and unpublished project data, resulting in data from 126 studies. These studies were then further examined to create a dataset of 62 studies in 16 countries relevant towards the intended tool creation. Biodiversity responses were quantified using log response ratios comparing agroforestry systems with conventional agricultural controls. Across the full dataset, agroforestry increased overall biodiversity by 16.0% on average, with stronger effects in silvopastoral systems (+23.4%) than in silvoarable systems (+11.8%).

Using mixed-effects, three-level meta-regression, we evaluated multiple model structures incorporating ecologically relevant moderators related to agroforestry design, management, system age, and landscape context. Model selection was based on repeated training–validation cycles, predictive accuracy (RMSE), and verification against independent validation subsets. The final model structure retained moderators describing plot type, woody species richness, shrub layer presence, system age, and woody habitat fraction and diversity in the surrounding landscape.

After retraining on the full dataset, six sub-models with acceptable predictive performance were retained, primarily capturing richness-related responses of natural enemies and overall biodiversity. In these models, because of the nature of the predictions, the residual heterogeneity remained high and confidence intervals were wide. In addition, model estimates showed prediction flaws in the three models of abundance, indicating that external model validation is still necessary despite the data-driven approach. The three remaining models were a model for biodiversity abundance/activity for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context, a model for mean species richness across agroforestry plots for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context and a model for total species richness across spatial units for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context.

The final output is an online decision-support tool that allows stakeholders to estimate biodiversity outcomes of agroforestry implementation under different scenarios. Although the current predictions are limited by data availability and heterogeneity, the open, updateable modelling framework provides a systematic and transparent basis for integrating new data and insights. Hence this deliverable can potentially provide an evidence-based method towards providing system and site-specific guidance on the impact of agroforestry on biodiversity, with potential benefits for agroforestry policy, management, and value-chain initiatives.

Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. A participatory research approach is key to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders and multiple research domains to facilitate the implementation of innovations. An overall objective of the project is to provide three groups of stakeholders with digital tools that address their needs and expectation. The three groups of stakeholders addressed by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This deliverable (D3.4) introduces and presents the establishment of a tool and its implementation into an RShiny application for estimating biodiversity effects generated by agroforestry implementation across Europe. It forms part of Work Package 3 in the DigitAF project which deals with the verification and accounting of the benefits of agroforestry practices for stakeholders in the value chain. An anticipated outcome of the work package is an enhanced capacity of actors to identify and account for the economic, environmental and social synergies and trade-offs of agroforestry.

D3.4 arises from Task 3.3 which has the objective of co-developing, applying and verifying a tool to quantify the biodiversity impact of agroforestry, which was validated through field work in different European regions. This report describes the development and functioning of the targeted biodiversity tool, through a data-driven approach with existing, published data. We developed a science- and evidence-based tool based on actual field data and compiled through meta-analysis regressions. The biodiversity data were used for training the model and for validation. An advantage of the new tool compared to e.g. the often-used expert-based and unitless credit point system, is that specific interactions are integrated in the tool such as biodiversity outputs on different functional biodiversity groups, potential mediating effects of the surrounding landscape, and system characteristics. This new tool can be used to inform both farmers and advisors implementing agroforestry, and policy actors about the biodiversity impacts of agroforestry.

1 Introduction

Sustainable agroecosystems can provide food, fibre and fodder alongside biodiversity and other ecosystem services such as pest control, pollination, nutrient cycling, and carbon drawdown (Dainese et al., 2019; Lindemann-Matthies et al., 2010; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Despite its importance, biodiversity is under threat (Butchart et al., 2010; Sachs et al., 2009). Policy actors increasingly recognize this problem (European Commission, 2011) and are taking initiatives for biodiversity conservation across Europe such as the Green Deal and the Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 (European Commission & Directorate-General for Environment, 2021).

The expansion and intensification of agriculture has been one of the key drivers of biodiversity decline in the last decades, mainly caused by the loss and degradation of natural and semi-natural habitats (Balmford et al., 2012; Tilman et al., 2001; Tschardt et al., 2012). Introducing trees and shrubs on intensive-managed agricultural land is one way of enhancing the biodiversity and ecosystem services on that land (Leakey, 1996). Woody elements can also present co-benefits by producing marketable products such as fuelwood, nuts, fruit, cork, and timber. This integration of woody species with farming is termed agroforestry. There are a range of agroforestry practices including silvoarable systems (i.e., tree-crop associations), silvopastoral systems and forest-grazing practices (i.e., tree-livestock associations), hedgerows and windbreaks, food forests, and scattered solitary trees. (Dmuchowski et al., 2024; Mosquera-Losada et al., 2009). Agroforestry increases habitat, food and shelter provision in combination with an increased diversification of resources (Jose, 2009; McAdam et al., 2009). However, because the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry depend on the baseline crop or livestock system, the age of the system, tree species, management and surrounding landscape (Kletty et al., 2023), analyses can present mixed results (Imbert et al., 2020; Mupepele et al., 2021; Pardon et al., 2019; Plieninger et al., 2015; Varah et al., 2020).

With the current biodiversity crisis in mind, it is important to improve our capacity to quantify the possible biodiversity gains owing to agroforestry, certainly since European legislation is aiming to connect carbon sequestration and biodiversity co-benefits (Lawson et al., 2020). A science-based tool allowing stakeholders to estimate the benefits of biodiversity due to agroforestry is thus urgently needed (Birrer et al., 2014; Dwyer et al., 2023; Vandendriessche, Eeraerts, et al., 2025). Current agricultural tools for biodiversity assessment have only very limited options to be applied in an agroforestry context (Vandendriessche, Eeraerts, et al., 2025). Previous research has tried to capture overall biodiversity effects of agroforestry systems by using systematic review or meta-analysis-techniques (Kletty et al., 2023; Mupepele & Dormann, 2022; Staton et al., 2019; Torralba et al., 2016). However, the low current taxonomic resolution and system differentiation currently limits the application of such tools, although the underlying data do potentially provide the resolution needed for such applications (Vandendriessche, Eeraerts, et al., 2025).

Here we present the concept and establishment of a biodiversity tool for agroforestry applications. Such a tool might thus (1) enable farmers to assess and understand the potential biodiversity gains on their farms when implementing agroforestry and (2) provide a clear interpretable metric that can be used to inform actors downstream along the value-chain. For instance, for certification purposes, our tool might enable the appropriate labelling of agroforestry products, important to both farmers and value chain actors, including the end consumer. Our modelling framework is updateable based on *in situ* biodiversity data, making the framework open and dynamic. This framework results in statistical models to be used in a tool environment where end-users can assign system characterizations to obtain modelled biodiversity change for different biodiversity groups or metrics.

Box 1. Terminology used in this work

This work introduces a bespoke terminology to disentangle the process handled here. This box provides a quick overview on these terms to enhance understanding.

Data terminology:

- **Database:** *all experiment-level observations*
- **Dataset:** *purified datasets extracted from the database with treatment-control comparisons*

Modeling terminology:

- **Moderators:** *the selected variables that are used for final model decision*
- **Model structure:** *a fixed combination of moderators used for model fitting*
- **Sub-models:** *specific models fitted within one model structure and being verified along our internal framework*
- **Tool:** *the agglomerate of sub-models generated in the best model structure, processed through a ShinyR interface*

Data-subsetting

- **Mean plot richness:** *information on mean richness over a plot-based protocol*
- **Total richness:** *information on total richness of an agroforestry element/field*
- **Abundance/activity:** *information on biodiversity quantity (i.e., covers, counts, activity-density, ...) over a plot-based protocol*
- **Agroforestry-general:** *information on silvoarable (tree line/alley/field-wise), silvopastoral (tree line/grass strip/field-wise) or other agroforestry plots*
- **Silvoarable:** *information on silvoarable (tree line/alley/field-wise) plots*
- **Silvopastoral:** *information on silvopastoral (tree line/grass strip/field-wise) plots*

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset extraction

To start the development of the data-fed biodiversity tool, we extracted data from the individual case-studies of (i) agroforestry-meta-analyses (Mupepele et al., 2021; Staton et al., 2019; Torralba et al., 2016), and (ii) added the systematic silvoarable review by Kletty et al. (2023). More information on the reasoning behind the selection of these meta-analyses is available in Vandendriessche et al. (2025). We complemented this work with (iii) unpublished data gathered during the European project DigitAF (<https://digitaf.eu/>) and (iv) works mentioned in the assessed studies. Ultimately, the aim was to construct a robust and large database based on previous systematic literature searches done for the currently available reviews and meta-analyses.

For each screened case-study that applied at least one agroforestry treatment, we extracted mean effect sizes and, where available, standard deviation, standard error or confidence intervals that reported biodiversity metrics such as species richness, abundance and diversity/evenness as narrowly defined as possible concerning taxonomic group, site, year and treatment (i.e., agroforestry or control and plot-specific information: tree strip, alley, distance to nearest tree row). **Supplementary Information Text 1** gives a full overview of all information extracted in the process and all the case-studies assessed. The final database combines thus all available information from these case-studies (either in-text, in supplementary material, in raw data or by correspondence with the authors).

2.2 Dataset processing and filtering

The resulting database contains 14,738 observations (i.e. the mean value for a biodiversity metric of a specific taxonomic group in a specific site) for 126 studies. Next, thorough data cleaning was applied to obtain a usable meta-analysis dataset. All data cleaning steps are explained in **Supplementary Information Text 2**.

Ratio of Means effect sizes (ROM; Log Response Ratio) were then calculated using the *escalc* function from the R-package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010) (Equation 1). The dataset comprises 68,404 effect sizes (treatment versus control; i.e. gain or loss of biodiversity due to agroforestry in comparison with a control system for a biodiversity metric of a specific taxonomic group in a specific site) overall, of which 12,940 unique values from 103 studies, excluding entries that were duplicated through multiple use of taxonomic groups across different biodiversity predictors. For example, a study that reports on carabids only, will provide duplicated results for those carabids for “overall” biodiversity and natural enemies, et cetera. Hence, *strictu senso*, these are duplicated entries.

$$ROM = \ln\left(\frac{\mu_{treatment}}{\mu_{control}}\right) \quad \mu = mean \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Next, only effect sizes comparing silvoarable, silvopastoral and agroforestry-general treatments with agricultural controls (respectively arable systems, pastures and agroecosystems in general) were selected for further modelling. Our final dataset included 62 studies and had 29,091 effect sizes (of which 11,847 unique) over 175 sites across 16 countries comparing agroforestry sites with conventional controls.

2.3 Moderator selection

In total, we compiled a total of 28 potential environmental covariates. Although, most of these variables are not uniformly present throughout the data, are colinear to each other or present random variability. In **Supplementary Information Text 3** more information is given on all these variables and their correlations. As our model framework aims to include the use of multiple moderators, we need to select moderators properly. Hox (2010) states that testing multiple moderators in a single model after (potential) moderating effects have been evaluated separately in univariate models, is a reasonable strategy. Hence, we decided to select ecologically relevant and uncorrelated variables that showed significant effects in the data (**Supplementary Information Text 3**).

2.4 Model selection

To determine the optimal set of fixed variables used as moderators in the predictive model, we constructed model structures (i.e., combination of moderators) that were modelled through the *rma.mv* function in the metafor package (Viechtbauer, 2010) with method Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML). We applied mixed effect, three level metaregression (i.e., a metaregression that incorporated layers in the random intercepts, these layers are variation between extracted effect sizes (level 1), variation in one study (level 2), and variation between studies (level 3); (Assink & Wibbelink, 2016). As random effects we chose 'Site ID' nested within 'Study ID'. As moderators, we considered the fixed variables: plot type characterization ($AF_{plottype}$), woody richness ($Tree_{SR}$), presence of shrub layer ($Shrub_{layer}$), age of the system (Age), woody habitat fraction in the surrounding landscape ($forestshrub_{frac}$), Shannon landscape diversity ($landscape_{shannon}$), presence of woody species needing animal pollination ($Tree_{pol}$), alley width ($Alley_{width}$), Climate ($Climate$), crop type ($Crop_{group}$), organic or conventional management (Org_{Conv}) and grazing density ($grazing_{dens}$) (Equation 2). Again, a more detailed description of these moderators is available in **Supplementary Information Text 3**.

Model structures were built with five basic moderators (bold) and all mutual combinations with the optional moderators. Colored moderators were specific to agroforestry types: **brown** for silvoarable and **green** for silvopasture. Both silvoarable moderators were always included together.

$$y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AF_{plottype} + \beta_2 \mathbf{Woody}_{SR} + \beta_3 \mathbf{Shrub}_{layer} + \beta_4 \mathbf{Age} + \beta_5 \mathbf{forestshrub}_{frac} + \beta_6 \mathbf{landscape}_{shannon} + \beta_7 \mathbf{Tree}_{pol} + \beta_8 \mathbf{Alley}_{width} + \beta_9 \mathbf{Climate} + \beta_{10} \mathbf{Crop}_{group} + \beta_{11} \mathbf{Org}_{Conv} + \beta_{12} \mathbf{grazing}_{dens} + u_i + r_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Equation 2

$$u_i \sim N(0, \tau^2) \quad \text{between study random intercept}$$
$$r_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2) \quad \text{within study random intercept}$$
$$\varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \text{variance}_{ij}) \quad \text{known sampling error}$$

i : study; j : effect size

The final model structure was then decided based on the following process, being repeated three times (**Figure 1**):

- We set-aside a part of the data for validation. The dataset was thus divided in a training set (containing 89.0-91.5% of the data) and a validation set (containing 8.5-11.0% of the data), randomly subsetted by adding separate studies to the validation set until the 8.5-11% criterion was met (since we selected complete studies, reaching exactly 10% was not possible). For these sets, the applied model structure was fitted over all potential subsets identified for each biodiversity group, biodiversity metric and agroforestry type.
- Since small sample sizes affect accuracy of the estimates and the width of confidence intervals (Cheung, 2014; Seide et al., 2019), requirements were installed for models to fit addressing the number of clusters (i.e., studies and sites), rather than effect sizes (Deeks et al., 2019). Models were only fitted when the number of studies in the training data exceeded 10 (previous research stated that meta-regression should not be considered with less than 10 studies; Van Den Noortgate and Onghena, 2003) and the number of sites in those studies exceeded 30 (Maas and Hox, 2005). Simultaneously, potential data transformations for continuous variables were tested after which the best combination of transformations (based on the RMSE (Root Mean Square Error)) were retained. Eight potential transformations were considered and two were selected per applied moderator to test during modelling. More information on this selection is available in **Supplementary Information Text 3**. Since we target a broad-audience biodiversity tool, predictive capacity and especially verified predictive quality are key. Therefore, we excluded any models with RMSE higher than five and then fitted models (function *lm* in base R) with the following syntax (Equation 3):

$$prediction_{metafor} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * validation + \varepsilon_i \quad \varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (prediction_{metafor} - validation)^2} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

- Next, we calculated p-values on slope (β_1) and intercept (β_0). Well-fitting models ideally should maintain a relation between predictions and validation observations corresponding with slope equalling one (1:1 diagonal) and without intercept bias. Therefore, we removed any models where slope significantly differed from one and intercept significantly differed from zero (F-test, function *linearHypothesis* in package *car* (Fox and Weisberg, 2019)). An important observation was that model fits could not impute the large heterogeneity in the raw data. This resulted in systematic underestimation for large raw data values (e.g., ROM ~ 2; corresponding with +640%) and overestimation at the opposite ends (e.g., ROM ~ -2; corresponding with -86%), see **Figure 4b**. It is possible that generated models cannot cope with the large heterogeneity present across biodiversity research and present mediated values. Since those mediated predictions have a much narrower distribution than the raw data, the linear regression slope between both tends to deviate from 1 (**Figure 4a**). Therefore, models with slopes different from 1, but between 0.15 and 1 (representing this mediating effect) were retained as well, as low-confidence models. This method represents thus a pragmatic approach with arbitrary choices, while trying to guarantee that predictions are still a proper match to raw data.
- For each tested model structure, we re-evaluated overall performance of the verified models by comparing validation set predictions with raw validation data and calculated overall model

structure RMSE and the number of models generated in the process (this metric is meaningful since the goal is to provide users with models for multiple agroforestry types and species groups, herewith we reduce the chances of selecting a coincident model structure where only one or two models are fitted with few validation data, artificially reducing RMSE). We performed z-transformations on these metrics to enable a ranking amongst model structures, although awarded RMSE a higher weight factor since this metric increases fit quality the most (Equation 4).

$$Z_{transformed} = \frac{column - mean(column)}{sd(column)}$$

$$Z_{score} = 2 * Z_{RMSE} + Z_{n_models} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Figure 1. Schematic approach of the applied framework. In a first run, a decision is made on the variables to be integrated as model moderators, based on an independent 10% validation set and 90% training data set, repeated three times. In a second step, the selected set of variables is fitted to the full dataset, with internal fit verification to retain a final model set to be used in the tool.

2.5 Full model

The final tool was trained on our complete dataset to fit the model on as much data as possible, applying the model structure that performed best in previous step. Again, models were only fitted when the number of studies and the number of sites was 10 and 30 or higher. Again, the same data transformations for continuous variables were tested and the best combination of transformations (based on the RMSE criterion) was kept (Equation 5). In this case, an independent validation set did not exist, so we evaluated prediction quality with the raw data used as training data (using 100% of this dataset). We excluded models with RMSE higher than five and then applied the model syntax below (function *lm* in base R). For well-fitting models, the relation between predictions and raw data observations should correspond with a linear trend on the 1:1 diagonal. Therefore, we removed any models where slope significantly differed from one and intercept significantly differed from zero (F-test, function *linearHypothesis* in package *car* (Fox and Weisberg, 2019)). However, similarly to previous step, models with slopes different from 1, but between 0.15 and 1 were retained as well, as low-confidence models.

$$prediction_{metafor} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * rawdata + \varepsilon_i \quad \varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (prediction_{metafor} - rawdata)^2} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

2.6 Tool implementation

The resulting models are saved locally in the framework and can be called upon in a Rshiny tool (Attali, 2021) where moderator states can be adapted manually. For the user-indicated moderator states, the mean estimated effect predicted by the model is returned as a log-transformed Ratio of Means. Results are back-transformed to percentages to be easier to interpret by users.

$$\% \text{ change} = e^{ROM} * 100\% - 100\%$$

Covariate $AF_{plottype}$ does not define the ecological system, but represents spatial plot layout difference. Towards the estimation of biodiversity gain throughout the system, this information is less relevant. So instead of choosing agroforestry plot type in the UI (user interface), we compute predictions for all agroforestry plot type levels considered and average over those:

$$Pred_{averaged} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K (Pred_k)$$

Further information on used packages is available in **Supplementary Information Text S4**.

3 Results

3.1 Dataset

Most studies in our database focused on arthropod life and autotrophs. A lot of information on functional group levels was present, except for pollinators, where the available data seem to be lagging behind despite wide stakeholder interest (**Figure S1**, (Tranchina et al., 2024)). Specific taxonomic resolution is often much lower in comparison with stakeholder's interest.

The dataset with agricultural controls was compiled for overall biodiversity across all agroforestry types and metrics (4152 effect sizes, *rma.mv*, restricted maximum likelihood, random term = Study/Site). The overall biodiversity gain of agroforestry across the dataset was 0.1548 (+16.7%) [0.0437, 0.2659] ($p = 0.0063$). **Figure 2** represents the corresponding effects for each individual study, while **Figure S2** represents effects over each individual effect size. Additionally, we repeated these analyses for subsets on the different agroforestry types tackled in this study. The biodiversity gain depended on applied system: the mean effect of agroforestry-general was 0.1482 (+16.0%) [0.0384, 0.2580] ($p = 0.0081$), the mean effect of silvoarable systems was 0.1113 (+11.8%) [-0.0139, 0.2365] ($p = 0.0815$) and the mean effect of silvopastoral systems was 0.2103 (+23.4%) [0.0353, 0.3853] ($p = 0.0185$). **Table S1** and **Table S2** give a detailed overview on analyses over several biodiversity groups and metrics.

Figure 2. The forest plot over studies, with indication of the overall estimate. Effect sizes were aggregated to the study level by fitting a fixed-effects meta-analysis to all observations originating from the same study (since the dataset integrated site-, plot- and metric differences). Red shaded area represents negative effects on biodiversity while green shaded area represents positive effects on biodiversity. Log Response Ratio = logarithmic Ratio of Means.

3.2 Model structure selection

In total, we evaluated 38 different model structures (with three repetitions) with independent sampled data and present herewith the five best according to overall RMSE and the number of sub-models with slope being not significantly different from one. **Figure 3** presents prediction-versus-validation data plots over all evaluated submodels, whilst **Table 1** gives specifications of the linear regressions across the sub-models. The fourth model structure has very little validation entries, resulting in low, but potential biased RMSE. The first model structure has most validation points, all relatively close the 1:1 slope line.

Figure 3. Prediction versus validation data plot for all sub-models combined for the top five model structures. (brown: silvoarable-specific moderators, green: silvopastoral-specific moderators). Basic moderators implement plot type characterization, woody richness, presence of shrub layer, age of the system and woody habitat fraction in the surrounding landscape. *landscape_shannon* = Shannon landscape diversity, *Tree.pol* = presence of woody species needing animal pollination, *Crop_group* = crop type, *Org.Conv* = organic or conventional management and *grazing_dens* = grazing density.

Table 1. Top five model structures. (brown: silvoarable-specific moderators, green: silvopastoral-specific moderators). Basic moderators implement plot type characterization, woody richness, presence of shrub layer, age of the system and woody habitat fraction in the surrounding landscape. Further on: *landscape_shannon* = Shannon landscape diversity, *Tree.pol* = presence of woody species needing animal pollination, *Crop_group* = crop type, *Org.Conv* = organic or conventional management and *grazing_dens* = grazing density.

	Raw data values in error margin (%)	RMSE	Number of sub-models
Base + <i>landscape_shannon</i>	62.88	0.877	16
Base + Climate + <i>Soil_type</i> + <i>Org.Conv</i> + <i>Crop_group</i> + <i>grazing_dens</i>	69.53	1.289	12
Base + <i>Alley.width</i> + <i>Soil_type</i> + <i>Org.Conv</i> + <i>Crop_group</i> + <i>grazing_dens</i>	81.88	0.831	9
Base + <i>Soil_type</i> + <i>Tree.pol</i>	81.08	0.456	6
Base + Climate + <i>landscape_shannon</i> + <i>Alley.width</i> + <i>Org.Conv</i> + <i>Crop_group</i> + <i>grazing_dens</i>	63.36	0.943	6

3.3 Final model structure

Over three runs the best scoring model structure retained 16 sub-models (fitted on different dataset subsets, hereafter referred to as sub-models) for which the linear slope (β_1) did not differ from one. The RMSE over all retained sub-models was 0.88. Independent validation data fitted in the confidence interval in 62.9% of all validation entries (**Table 1**). The final model structure was then (Equation 6):

$$\begin{aligned} prediction = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 AF_{plottype} + \beta_2 Woody_{SR} + \beta_3 Shrub_{layer} \\ & + \beta_4 Age + \beta_5 forestshrub_{frac} + \beta_6 landscape_{shannon} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$Age \sim \log(Age)$$

$$forestshrub_{frac} \sim 1 + \exp\left(\frac{forestshrub_{frac}}{100}\right)$$

$$landscape_{shannon} \sim 1 + \exp(landscape_{shannon})$$

Fitting this model structure over the complete dataset with internal fit verification resulted in the retention of six final sub-models:

- (i) a model for abundance/activity for aboveground invertebrates in silvoarable context,
- (ii) a model for abundance/activity for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context,
- (iii) a model for mean species richness across agroforestry plots for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context,
- (iv) a model for total species richness across spatial units for natural enemies in broad agroforestry context,
- (v) a model for abundance/activity for overall biodiversity in broad agroforestry context and
- (vi) a model for abundance/activity for pollinators in broad agroforestry context.

All final sub-models were fitted with a logarithmic transformation for *Age* and with a reversed exponential transformation on *forestshrub_{frac}* and *landscape_{shannon}*. None of these sub-models had a slope that wasn't significantly different from one when fitting the predictions to the raw data. Especially models (ii), (iii) and (iv) show well that predictions cannot catch up with raw data heterogeneity. The other models (especially (i) and (v)) show very divergent effect sizes (**Figure 4a**). Additionally, the residual plots in **Figure 4b** emphasize the fact of underestimating large raw data values and overestimating small raw data values.

Figure 4. (a) Training data values versus model predictions plot per submodel retained. (b) Residuals (prediction – raw training data) along the model predictions. All values are presented as Ratio of Means. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, ab = bundance/activity, SR = mean plot richness, totSR = total richness. Faded trends appoint slope trends significantly differing from one-to-one predictions. In this particular case no non-differing sub-models were fitted.

Moderator *Age* systematically had a (small) negative coefficients for richness sub-models (**Table 2**). In order to explore this, separate univariate meta-analyses were performed to explore this observation. **Table S3** and **Table S4** confirm this trend for the relevant sub-models, whereas especially abundance shows a different trend. Early-agroforestry-age research observations suggest a more complex mitigating effect of age than potentially capped with the transformations used (**Figure S3**), but there is too little data present for such young systems to cap this trend properly (**Figure S4**). In response to these early-age discrepancies, our tool will only display age effects from the fifth year on.

Additionally, we explored trends for $Tree_{SR}$ and $forestshrub_{frac}$. The $Tree_{SR}$ model estimates for abundance/activity models returned high estimates (i.e. ± 1), which was potentially biased by the lesser amount of effect sizes with multiple woody genera present (**Figure S6**) and which is higher than what overall univariate models suggest (**Figure S5**). For $forestshrub_{frac}$ high estimates were returned as well, but the nature of the reversedexp-transformation does not lead to odd effect sizes (**Figure S7**). Most effect sizes situate between a zero and 25% woody habitat fraction (**Figure S8**).

Table 2. Model coefficients. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, Bold values are significant. ($AF_{plotype}$ = plot type characterization, $Tree_{SR}$ = woody richness, $Shrub_{layer}$ = presence of shrub layer, $forestshrub_{frac}$ = woody habitat fraction in the surrounding landscape, $landscape_{shannon}$ = Shannon landscape diversity)

	Abundance/ activity for overall biodiversity	Abundance/ activity for soil-related arthropods	Mean plot richness across agroforestry plots for natural enemies	Abundance/ activity for natural enemies	Total richness across spatial unit for natural enemies	Abundance/ activity for pollinators
Intercept	-18.440 [-22.25, -14.63]	-6.881 [-11.76, -2.01]	1.563 [-0.15, 3.28]	-4.627 [-7.05, -2.20]	2.040 [-0.03, 4.11]	-9.004 [-13.95, -4.06]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvoarable	6.076 [3.49, 8.66]		0.214 [-1.09, 1.52]	1.780 [0.27, 3.29]	-0.127 [-1.75, 1.50]	2.438 [-0.68, 5.56]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvoarable alley	6.656 [4.07, 9.25]	0.219 [0.15, 0.28]	-0.325 [-1.63, 0.98]	1.565 [0.06, 3.07]	-0.684 [-2.31, 0.94]	1.548 [-1.53, 4.62]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvoarable tree line	7.218 [4.63, 9.81]	0.380 [0.26, 0.50]	-0.338 [-1.64, 0.97]	1.489 [-0.02, 3.00]	-0.724 [-2.35, 0.90]	1.736 [-1.34, 4.81]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvopastoral	5.177 [2.48, 7.87]		0.762 [-0.54, 2.06]	1.797 [0.25, 3.35]	0.579 [-1.04, 2.19]	2.369 [-0.81, 5.55]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvopastoral alley	4.881 [2.10, 7.66]		0.077 [-1.79, 1.94]	0.898 [-0.69, 2.49]	0.006 [-2.17, 2.18]	0.295 [-2.80, 3.39]
$AF_{plotype}$: Silvopastoral tree line	5.558 [2.78, 8.33]		0.379 [-1.48, 2.25]	1.523 [-0.05, 3.10]	0.308 [-1.87, 2.48]	1.525 [-1.56, 4.61]
Age	2.201 [2.10, 2.30]	1.071 [0.92, 1.22]	-0.141 [-0.27, -0.01]	0.659 [0.54, 0.78]	-0.257 [-0.43, -0.08]	0.703 [0.28, 1.13]
$Tree_{SR}$	1.116 [0.97, 1.27]	1.565 [1.35, 1.78]	0.019 [-0.05, 0.09]	0.038 [-0.07, 0.15]	0.013 [-0.07, 0.10]	0.938 [0.77, 1.11]
$Shrub_{layer}$: TRUE	-2.389 [-2.97, -1.81]	-3.006 [-4.16, -1.86]	0.290 [0.07, 0.51]	-0.041 [-0.48, 0.40]	0.288 [-0.01, 0.58]	-1.422 [-2.05, -0.80]
$forestshrub_{frac}$	8.405 [2.39, 14.42]	6.796 [-4.25, 17.84]	-1.962 [-4.02, 0.09]	1.746 [-1.84, 5.33]	-1.74 [-4.04, 0.56]	1.637 [-1.20, 13.41]
$landscape_{shannon}$	2.190 [-3.27, 7.65]	-9.040 [-20.92, 2.84]	-1.678 [-3.56, 0.20]	1.676 [-1.64, 4.98]	-1.68 [-3.79, 0.44]	0.640 [-4.46, 8.79]

3.4 Tool

The tool is available online with the following link: <https://biodivaf.shinyapps.io/BiodivAF/>. This link could change in future since it is now hosted on a ShinyApp server with restricted server time, meant for prototyping purpose, but not for general deployment. In future, hosting facilities might change. The underlying database (Vandendriessche, 2025) and the framework (Vandendriessche, Landuyt, et al., 2025) applied with a local version of this tool will be made publicly available after publication under following link: <https://github.com/JariVddr/BiodivAF>, in a shared repository with the EURAF (European Agroforestry Federation) GitHub account. This GitHub repository will always contain the link to the active tool.

At the tool stage, moderator $AF_{plotype}$ was no longer relevant to end users and results as such display a mediate effect across the levels of this moderator. Since models (i), (ii) and (vi) have very large absolute intercept values (>5) that are not mitigated by $AF_{plotype}$. We removed these sub-models from the final tool since such large absolute values have no interpretable ecological meaning.

3.5 Scenario testing

As a case-study, we explored tool outputs for four scenarios, representative to some of the agroforestry systems studied in DigitAF, and concerning different agroforestry systems. Nine of the 23 modelled biodiversity responses were positive (**Table 3**), but confidence intervals were wide indicating high variation. The abundance/activity models responded negatively in almost all cases, with a typical value of -90%. If we only consider the models with ecologically interpretable intercept values (<5), nine out of 12 outputs respond positively. The 11 estimates of the excluded sub-models vary between -72.1 and -99.4% and do not show significant influences throughout different designs, even though the systems taken as example vary highly, supporting the premise of removing those models from the final tool.

Table 3. Four example scenarios (with representative areas indicated) for model testing and predictions for applied models. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable. For the applied terminology we kindly refer to **Supplementary Text S1**. Red shaded sub-models have large intercept values with little ecological meaning.

	Scenario 1: ~ Flanders	Scenario 2: ~ Flanders	Scenario 3: ~ Occitany	Scenario 4: ~ Extremadura
Climate type	Temperate	Temperate	Mediterranean	Mediterranean
Fraction of cropland area	50%	30%	30%	1%
Fraction of woody habitat	25%	10%	30%	40%
Landscape diversity	1.15	1.40	1.60	0.70
Soil type	Loam	Clay	Loam	Loam
Agroforestry type	Silvoarable	Silvoarable	Silvoarable	Silvopastoral
Agroforestry age	13 y	13 y	30 y	60 y
Woody genera	<i>Sorbus, Salix, Corylus, ...</i>	<i>Populus</i>	<i>Juglans</i>	<i>Olea</i>
Woody richness	5	1	1	1
Shrub layer presence	Yes	No	No	No
Pollination potential trees	Yes	Yes	No	No
Alley width	24 m	24 m	14 m	10 m
Crop type	Cereals	Corn	Vegetables/Mass flowering crops	
Organic/conventional	Org	Conv	Conv	
Grazing density				Low
Abundance/activity for overall biodiversity	-94.9% [-99.7, -21.5]	-99.4% [-100.0, -91.5]	-96.5% [-99.8, -50.2]	-77.2% [-98.6, 274.2]
Abundance/activity for soil-related arthropods	-72.1% [-99.8, 3566.4]	-98.4% [-100.0, 93.6]	-94.9% [-100.0, 473.2]	
Mean plot richness for natural enemies	+290.2% [23.5, 1264.7]	+190.6% [-6.5, 900.2]	+171.6% [-11.0, 816.9]	+87.1% [-39.9, 543.3]
Abundance/activity for natural enemies	-61.5% [-92.7, 106.9]	-67.9% [-93.6, 63]	-47.0% [-89.3, 165.7]	+10.1% [-78.6, 474.6]
Total richness across spatial unit for natural enemies	+278.4% [-5.0, 1608.5]	+189.7% [-22.8, 1143.2]	+145.7% [-33.0, 927.1]	+56.2% [-58.1, 563.1]
Abundance/activity plots for pollinators	-81.4% [-99.4, 452.1]	-98.4% [-99.9, -50.9]	-97.2% [-99.9, -27.0]	-93.5% [-99.8, 108.6]

4 Tool interface

This section includes some screenshots of the “Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator” beta version.

Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (beta)

Introduction

This web application provides estimated biodiversity responses to agroforestry implementation in European climatic context based on existing case-studies and published scientific data. More than 100 separate case-studies were included in the predictive modelling approach towards this tool. For more information and the scientific background of this tool, please refer to the bibliography section below.

Purpose

The purpose of this tool is to inform stakeholders like farmers, policy actors or anyone with interest in agroforestry about potential biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems in comparison to conventional monoculture agricultural systems. It allows users to explore how different agroforestry configurations and landscape contexts may influence biodiversity outcomes. Ideally, this tool, in future formats, can support decision-making on agroforestry adoption and design to maximize biodiversity benefits.

Background

The development of this tool is part of the DigitAF project (digitaf.eu/). This European project focuses on the provision of open-source digital tools for stakeholders to understand effects of agroforestry implementations for agricultural resilience.

During the data assemblage for this tool, biodiversity results were collected on site- and group specific scale to enable predictions on different agroforestry set-ups across different biodiversity groups.

The results are derived from published scientific data and reflect predicted percentage changes relative to conventional agricultural systems. These outputs should be interpreted as indicative trends rather than exact forecasts, as ecological responses are context-dependent and influenced by multiple interacting factors.

This tool integrates statistical models accounting for landscape structure, management practices, and system age. It is designed to support decision-making, research exploration and scenario comparison.

Future options of development

The work presented here is far from complete. The current tool, comparing agroforestry with baseline agriculture systems without trees, is based on 62 case-studies, while potentially (much) more data is already published, either internationally or nationally. Adding new datasets to the framework behind this tool might enable better predictions, the fit of more model options and the integration of more system-dependent parameters.

Current restrictions prohibit modelling for silvopastoral systems to large extent, but the integration of more studies, or the data provision of more site-specific results might enhance model requirements. Also the addition of more agroforestry systems, like food forests, are potentially possible, if there is sufficient data to be analyzed.

Also comparison of agroforestry to other systems, like forests is a future possibility.

Figure A. Screenshot of page 1 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator: Introduction and information towards users.

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Figure B. Screenshot of page 1 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator: Bibliography, Contact and Acknowledgments.

Select biodiversity metrics

First select the agroforestry system type and the biodiversity indicators you wish to explore.

Agroforestry System Type:

← Back

Go to modelling tool →

Figure C. Screenshot of page 2 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator before any agroforestry type is selected.

Select biodiversity metrics

First select the agroforestry system type and the biodiversity indicators you wish to explore.

Agroforestry System Type:
Agroforestry

	*	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	*	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	*	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

* Models marked with an asterisk showed low predictive performance and should be interpreted with caution.

[← Back](#) [Go to modelling tool →](#)

Figure D. Screenshot of page 2 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator after selection of agroforestry type.

Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (beta)

Fraction of woody habitat in a 1km radius (%):
0 10 100

Landscape diversity:
0.12 1.04

Extreme Low Low Medium High Extreme High

Woody species richness:
1

Are shrub species present in the agroforestry element?

Age of the agroforestry system (years):
0.5 15 60

[← Back](#) [Run Model](#)

Figure E. Screenshot of page 3 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator before running the tool.

Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator (beta)

Fraction of woody habitat in a 1km radius (%)

0 10 100

Landscape diversity:

0.12 1.94

Extreme Low Low Medium High Extreme High

Woody species richness:

1

Are shrub species present in the agroforestry element?

Age of the agroforestry system (years):

0.5 15 60

← Back

Run Model

Group	Metric	Agroforestry type	Prediction (%)	lower confidence (%)	upper confidence (%)
Natural enemies	Abundance/activity	Agroforestry	-44.3	-91.0	252.1
Natural enemies	Mean plot richness	Agroforestry	80.3	-48.5	592.4
Natural enemies	Total richness	Agroforestry	76.9	-58.5	751.4

Figure F. Screenshot of page 3 of the Agroforestry Biodiversity Gain Estimator after running the tool.

5 Discussion

In this report, we have established an evidence-based biodiversity assessment tool for agroforestry. We constructed predictive models in a triple-fold validation process with training data and independent validation data subsetted per loop. Afterwards, the tool was retrained on the complete dataset with internal fit checks in the framework and careful interpretation of tool estimates. Much of this approach is deducted from previous predictive modelling frameworks (such as Wen et al., 2024), but could not be followed entirely. The red markings in **Figure 5** highlights items that could be added in future versions of the framework presented. For example, an error rate could be calculated with an externally separated dataset as independent validation. However, such subsetting of the available data was, in our opinion, not possible since it would dilute the main dataset too much. Secondly, working within the highly variable context of both agroforestry and biodiversity, we had to implement more relaxed restrictions to ensure sub-models were retained. However, despite these limitations, we believe that our tool contains a useful and substantial advance for modelling the effects of agroforestry on biodiversity. Although the model predicts broad confidence intervals, this is a result of data collected on-site, in a variety of locations and sampling techniques, which both ensures the robustness and generality of the tool, but at the same time entails a lower precision.

Figure 5. Schematic approach of the framework applied ideally. In a first run, a decision is made on the variables to be integrated as model moderators, based on an independent 10% validation set and 90% training data set, repeated 10 times. The best structure is validated with an independent dataset, never used as training set. In a second step, the selected set of variables is fitted to the full dataset. Red colors represent potential for future feature additions in the framework.

Despite the progress, the implemented set-up has limitations. For example, three of the six models (abundance for overall biodiversity, abundance for soil related arthropods, and abundance for pollinators) in the framework showed high absolute values among model estimates and are thus considered to be unreliable. While trying to capture biodiversity responses through agroforestry type, biodiversity groups and metrics, a stringent data dilution was performed throughout the dataset for each sub-model, limiting the power of these models and thus risking overparameterization. Internal

prediction checks should normally preserve the predictive quality of returned sub-models, but this ability is limited. Across the sub-models, residual heterogeneity remained high. Again, this points to the heterogenous nature of our dataset, both among and within studies. In addition, no interactions were tested in this framework and exploration of some continuous variables suggested more complex trends than the transformations considered.

The dataset used here contains valuable information on biodiversity observations across agroforestry studies and was aimed to be collected efficiently while presenting a high-resolution overview of scientific work performed. We did not carry out a systematic literature search to gather new material published after the selection data criteria of Kletty et al. (2023) as the goal here was to converge to a well-applied biodiversity assessment tool, rather than an exhaustive meta-analysis. The explorative analysis of our dataset showed diverse effects, confirming observations made by previous meta-analyses (Mupepele et al., 2021; Torralba et al., 2016), but mainly appointed a positive effect on biodiversity metrics, especially for richness effects. However, we are well-aware that the global effect we analyzed now might be biased to certain extents. Overall, surveyed agroforestry systems tend to be young (between 5 and 15 years), and surveyed (and compared) plot-wise.

One argument for finding diverging biodiversity effects is that the main effect of agroforestry is caused by the structural diversity created in-field. This partially leads to plot-wise observed spill-over effects (Pardon et al., 2019), but mainly increases field-level biodiversity (in the assumption that beta diversity among the woody feature and the agricultural basis is high). **Table S2** assesses analyses over field-level richness where 10 out of 19 analyses showed positive outcomes. In comparison, there were 33 significant effects out of 96 analyses in **Table S1**, one being negative. This opens up avenues for more detailed analyses, which were out of the scope of this report, since its focuses on providing a pragmatic tool for farmers end policy-makers.

Obviously, regarding the complexity of biodiversity data (across taxa, sampling techniques, temporal and spatial facets) and agroforestry (differences in design, management), data heterogeneity is high among and within studies. Staton et al. (2019) argued that, especially in temperate regions, both the practical knowledge and scientific understanding of the effects of agroforestry on biodiversity were still limited. Currently, investments are being made to address the lack of practical knowledge by providing factsheets and tools (Bliss et al., 2019; Tomás et al., 2024; Vandendriessche, 2025) to guide decision making by land owners, but scientific understanding of the interacting effects of management and environmental circumstances on biodiversity in agroforestry system is still limited (Kletty et al., 2023) and often deduced from experiences in other agroecosystems. Current data availability might already support cross-study analyses to compute higher resolution effects than the meta-analyses now available.

Another limit lies in the scale at which moderators are considered. It might be possible to incorporate other moderating effects such as distance to tree, tree density, and landscape context. However, in each case, choices have to be made on what effects to be integrated since plot-wise effect sizes and field-wise effect size can behave differently. The database produced here could be used to analyze these metrics in future, thanks to the variety of metrics that were collected in this work. However, some potentially interesting metrics could not be collected, such as detailed design metrics and management approaches, because they are less often reported in publications, so knowledge on these topics remains limited.

Our current database shows that there is existing potential to support more detailed cross-study analyses than yet present, but also reveals data discrepancies for different taxonomic (e.g., bats, moths, earthworms) and agroforestry type (e.g., food forests) coverages and unbalances across site characteristics. Many silvopastoral studies report effect sizes at study scale which causes site-level dilution of effect sizes, while silvoarable studies more often report field characteristics (and responses) since substantial habitat differences are often perceived at field level. *De facto*, this means that there are lesser observations in silvopastoral contexts and, more importantly, lesser site clusters, limiting the options for our predictive framework.

An unbalanced dataset for age and introduced woody richness also made model fitting more difficult. Especially for very young agroforestry systems (1-2 years), there is a lack of evidence across different taxonomic groups. Although the impacts on biodiversity are not expected to be large, an absence of observations leads to bias in the fitting of the models.

There is potential for future research to accumulate an update of available temperate agroforestry data towards better compiling options and better model fits towards biodiversity assessment across agroforestry designs. Although scientific research on this topic is accelerating at pace, there has been no systematic search has been conducted for case-studies since Kletty et al. (2023). Even with systematic searches, some information also gets overlooked such as da Silva et al. (2008), Jakobsson & Lindborg (2017) and Tárrega et al. (2006). It might be effective as well to look for grey and non-English literature specifically to gain on spatial coverage, which is now especially western-European-biased. Moreover, some collected data is not made publicly available. One of the objectives of the DigitAF project is the promote the public availability of both agroforestry tools and data. By using additional data, there is the potential for increasing the resolution of this kind of modelling exercise.

Overall, the tool in its current form focuses on some specifically selected biodiversity metrics in a limited amount of agroforestry types. This is largely due to data-dilution through subsetting across those typologies as fewer data complicates model fitting. However, the framework used form a baseline analysis for future data compiling, addition and model expansion. Even the current database has not been fully exploited. For example, it also integrates other controls than a pure monoculture control (e.g., forest, field margins) and contains additional information on hedgerows as an additional agroforestry type. Moreover, the framework is implemented in a structured way, which will be made open source through a GitHub repository as a living environment (<https://github.com/JariVddr/BiodivAF>; Vandendriessche, Landuyt, et al., 2025). The database is published in a folder with one csv-file per study, enabling easy addition of studies by adding new csv-files or adapting existing records with more detailed observations, new taxa or new variables. Existing scripts can then perform the finetuning of the dataset, the selection of the best model structure and the sub-model updates for the model.

6 Way-forward

As a next step we will publish these results in an internationally peer-reviewed scientific journal and update the tool with extended analyses. The implementation is created in an automated way to enhance future updates and especially data additions.

In particular, data from the field work conducted during DigitAF project needs to be completed. For the broad-spectrum biodiversity field work campaign in 2024 across 31 separate sites throughout Europe, most species groups are still being identified. These sites consist of both silvoarable and silvopastoral systems and were evenly distributed in five localities across the DigitAF consortium partners (Portugal, southern France, Belgium, Czechia and the UK) to ensure a broad site heterogeneity. The broad-spectrum biodiversity metrics will include information on avian (birds), chiropteran (bats), floral (vegetation) and arthropodal (pollinators, soil dwelling arthropods, natural enemies, decomposers, ...) diversity, counting for more than 10 taxonomic groups. A multi-taxonomic study will be carried out and afterwards, the complete dataset will be fed to the tool.

Finally, the existence of these project outputs needs to be communicated to the end user through various information channels. As such, the tool, in its existing form is available online and added to databases established through the project in Deliverable 4.5: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-and-data-catalogue/> (Palma et al., 2024). The existing GitHub repository will be made open to the public and transferred to the EURAF GitHub account to improve visibility and potential future work. In **March 2026**, the tool presented in this report will be presented in a DigitAF-organised webinar focusing on biodiversity and soil health.

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Annex I – Supplementary figures

Species groups' relevance for stakeholders

Species groups studied in existing research

Supporting Information Figure S1. (a) A barplot of percentage respondents valuing certain biodiversity groups according to the perception of importance, extracted from Vandendriessche et al. (2025). (b) A barplot of percentage of previously applied studies in agroforestry contexts where comparisons to control plots were made (103 studies). Groups were not always comparable one-to-one due to subset-construction, following changes were applied: plants → autotrophs (+ lichens), other soil fauna → soil-related invertebrates (+ earthworms), other mammals → ground-dwelling vertebrates (+ herpetofauna), other arthropods → pest species (mainly pest species were not considered in the other arthropod groups). These alternations were also assigned in the plot labels. Species silhouettes were derived from phylopic.org. The colors of the silhouettes appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Supporting Information Figure S2. The forest plot over effect sizes, with indication of the overall estimate. Note the outliers at opposite sides (LROM -5 ~ -99.3% and LROM 7.5 ~ +180704,2%), being values that mediating models cannot catch in any sense. Red shaded area represents negative effects on biodiversity while green shaded area represents positive effects on biodiversity. ROM = logarithmic Ratio of Means.

Supporting Information Figure S3. Meta-analysis models for moderator Age for richness (SR) and abundance/activity (ab) metrics for the main agroforestry types considered, with the logarithmic regression fitted with *rma.mv*, *restricted maximum likelihood* and *random term = Study/Site*. Raw data points within the cropped area are visualized. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture. ROM = logarithmic Ratio of Means.

Supporting Information Figure S4. Number of effect sizes for the agroforestry-general subset for moderator Age. Clusters exist at 5-15, 20-30 and at 60 (or older). A decent number of effect sizes is present at very young stage (1-3), but since a lot of changes are ongoing then, more research might be needed to really understand what gain or losses are made then.

Supporting Information Figure S5. Meta-analysis models for moderator Age for richness (SR) and abundance/activity (ab) metrics for the main agroforestry types considered, with the logarithmic regression fitted with *rma.mv*, *restricted maximum likelihood* and *random term = Study/Site*. Raw data points within the cropped area are visualized. Legend: **blue** = *agroforestry-general*, **orange** = *silvoarable*, **green** = *silvopasture*. ROM = logarithmic Ratio of Means.

Supporting Information Figure S6. Number of effect sizes for the agroforestry-general subset for moderator Woody richness. Most observations are available for sites with only one genus present, making bias of model slope estimates possible.

Supporting Information Figure S7. Meta-analysis models for moderator Woody habitat fraction for richness (SR) and abundance/activity (ab) metrics for the main agroforestry types considered, with the logarithmic regression fitted with *rma.mv*, restricted maximum likelihood and random term = Study/Site. Raw data points within the cropped area are visualized. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture. ROM = logarithmic Ratio of Means.

Supporting Information Figure S8: Number of effect sizes for the agroforestry-general subset for moderator Woody habitat fraction. Most observations are available for sites with only one genus present, making bias of model slope estimates possible.

Annex II – Supplementary tables

Supporting Information Table S1. Meta-analyses (effect sizes presented in logarithmic Ratio of Means) for biodiversity richness and quantity (expressed in abundance, activity, biomass) metrics for comparisons between agroforestry and monoculture controls. Models fitted with rma.mv, restricted maximum likelihood and random term = Study/Site when the number of applied studies equalized or exceeded 5 and the number of sites studied equalized or exceeded 10. CI = 95% confidence interval, st = studies, eff = effect sizes. Legend: blue = agroforestry-general, brown = silvoarable, green = silvopasture. Fainter (not bold) values represent not significant results ($P < 0.05$). The colors of the species groups appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Species group	Metric	mean _{AF}	CI _{AF}	n _{AF}	mean _{SA}	CI _{SA}	n _{SA}	mean _{SP}	CI _{SP}	n _{SP}
Overall	Richness	0.224	[0.131, 0.316]	49 st, 656 eff	0.228	[0.121, 0.335]	33 st, 485 eff	0.208	[0.047, 0.368]	22 st, 161 eff
	Quantity	0.143	[-0.024, 0.309]	48 st, 666 eff	0.075	[-0.079, 0.228]	36 st, 514 eff	0.238	[-0.106, 0.583]	15 st, 142 eff
Arthropods	Richness	0.154	[0.064, 0.243]	27 st, 442 eff	0.184	[0.062, 0.305]	21 st, 366 eff	0.137	[0.006, 0.269]	11 st, 67 eff
	Quantity	-0.044	[-0.248, 0.160]	33 st, 440 eff	-0.018	[-0.237, 0.200]	25 st, 362 eff	-0.094	[-0.537, 0.349]	11 st, 70 eff
Aboveground invertebrates	Richness	0.229	[0.066, 0.391]	15 st, 157 eff	0.334	[0.165, 0.502]	12 st, 98 eff	0.103	[-0.080, 0.286]	8 st, 50 eff
	Quantity	-0.02	[-0.277, 0.236]	26 st, 232 eff	-0.031	[-0.323, 0.260]	20 st, 172 eff	0.051	[-0.298, 0.400]	9 st, 52 eff
Soil-related invertebrates	Richness	0.031	[-0.153, 0.215]	16 st, 366 eff	-0.04	[-0.317, 0.237]	12 st, 315 eff	0.146	[-0.005, 0.297]	6 st, 44 eff
	Quantity	0.014	[-0.197, 0.224]	23 st, 333 eff	0.06	[-0.166, 0.286]	18 st, 279 eff	-0.35	[-0.896, 0.196]	7 st, 50 eff
Autotrophs	Richness	0.276	[-0.036, 0.587]	16 st, 123 eff	0.561	[0.050, 1.071]	7 st, 85 eff	0.027	[-0.089, 0.144]	10 st, 30 eff
	Quantity	0.284	[-0.024, 0.592]	11 st, 145 eff	0.484	[-0.015, 0.984]	5 st, 109 eff	-0.019	[-0.193, 0.156]	6 st, 34 eff
Lichens	Richness			1 st, 1 eff						1 st, 1 eff
	Quantity									
Natural enemies	Richness	0.165	[-0.023, 0.354]	25 st, 467 eff	-0.08	[-0.327, 0.167]	17 st, 325 eff	0.346	[0.104, 0.587]	11 st, 133 eff
	Quantity	0.135	[-0.117, 0.388]	29 st, 407 eff	-0.103	[-0.298, 0.091]	21 st, 290 eff	0.468	[0.009, 0.927]	10 st, 110 eff
Spiders	Richness	-0.214	[-0.432, 0.005]	8 st, 121 eff	-0.373	[-0.778, 0.033]	5 st, 80 eff	0.073	[-0.076, 0.221]	5 st, 34 eff
	Quantity	-0.061	[-0.269, 0.146]	16 st, 158 eff	-0.045	[-0.331, 0.240]	12 st, 121 eff	-0.135	[-0.477, 0.207]	6 st, 33 eff
Beetles	Richness	0.031	[-0.067, 0.129]	10 st, 231 eff	0.037	[-0.072, 0.146]	7 st, 219 eff			2 st, 10 eff
	Quantity	-0.219	[-0.377, -0.061]	19 st, 272 eff	-0.287	[-0.497, -0.076]	15 st, 231 eff	0.16	[-0.263, 0.583]	5 st, 38 eff
Ladybugs	Richness			1 st, 4 eff						1 st, 4 eff
	Quantity	-0.083	[-0.270, 0.104]	6 st, 89 eff	-0.106	[-0.295, 0.083]	5 st, 81 eff			1 st, 8 eff
Staphylinids	Richness			1 st, 17 eff			1 st, 17 eff			
	Quantity			2 st, 13 eff			2 st, 13 eff			
Carabids	Richness	0.018	[-0.088, 0.124]	7 st, 219 eff	0.015	[-0.101, 0.130]	5 st, 209 eff			2 st, 10 eff
	Quantity	-0.171	[-0.376, 0.035]	9 st, 158 eff	-0.243	[-0.428, -0.058]	7 st, 143 eff			2 st, 15 eff
Ants	Richness									
	Quantity			4 st, 24 eff			4 st, 21 eff			1 st, 3 eff
Flying vertebrates	Richness	0.445	[0.154, 0.735]	11 st, 133 eff	0.235	[-0.208, 0.677]	7 st, 44 eff	0.491	[0.133, 0.850]	6 st, 89 eff
	Quantity	0.813	[0.256, 1.370]	6 st, 80 eff			3 st, 18 eff			4 st, 62 eff
Birds	Richness	0.629	[0.305, 0.952]	9 st, 88 eff	0.424	[0.101, 0.747]	6 st, 38 eff			4 st, 50 eff
	Quantity			4 st, 35 eff			2 st, 12 eff			2 st, 23 eff
Bats	Richness			2 st, 45 eff			1 st, 6 eff			2 st, 39 eff
	Quantity			2 st, 45 eff			1 st, 6 eff			2 st, 39 eff

Species group	Metric	mean _{AF}	CI _{AF}	n _{AF}	mean _{SA}	CI _{SA}	n _{SA}	mean _{SP}	CI _{SP}	n _{SP}
Pest species	Richness	0.244	[0.041, 0.448]	24 st, 165 eff	0.429	[0.145, 0.712]	15 st, 121 eff	0.029	[-0.090, 0.147]	11 st, 36 eff
	Quantity	-0.069	[-0.305, 0.166]	23 st, 262 eff	-0.089	[-0.417, 0.239]	16 st, 212 eff	-0.087	[-0.254, 0.080]	8 st, 49 eff
Gastropods	Richness			2 st, 19 eff			2 st, 19 eff			
	Quantity			4 st, 30 eff			3 st, 28 eff			1 st, 2 eff
Soil fauna	Richness	0.169	[0.056, 0.282]	16 st, 307 eff	0.176	[0.050, 0.301]	13 st, 284 eff			3 st, 16 eff
	Quantity	0.152	[-0.059, 0.364]	27 st, 306 eff	0.208	[-0.037, 0.453]	23 st, 272 eff	-0.394	[-1.060, 0.272]	6 st, 30 eff
Earthworms	Richness			2 st, 45 eff			1 st, 32 eff			1 st, 6 eff
	Quantity			4 st, 40 eff			2 st, 30 eff			2 st, 6 eff
Microbiota	Richness			4 st, 29 eff			4 st, 29 eff			
	Quantity	0.166	[-0.009, 0.342]	8 st, 44 eff	0.163	[-0.014, 0.339]	8 st, 44 eff			
Centipedes	Richness			1 st, 1 eff			1 st, 1 eff			
	Quantity	0.143	[-1.149, 1.435]	5 st, 25 eff	0.147	[-1.153, 1.447]	5 st, 25 eff			
Millipedes	Richness			3 st, 89 eff			3 st, 89 eff			
	Quantity	0.402	[-0.525, 1.329]	6 st, 56 eff	0.404	[-0.523, 1.331]	6 st, 56 eff			
Woodlice	Richness			2 st, 85 eff			2 st, 85 eff			
	Quantity	1.292	[0.459, 2.125]	7 st, 87 eff	1.418	[0.678, 2.158]	7 st, 83 eff			2 st, 4 eff
Pollinators	Richness	0.418	[0.299, 0.536]	10 st, 123 eff	0.481	[0.334, 0.628]	9 st, 83 eff	0.19	[-0.007, 0.386]	7 st, 33 eff
	Quantity	0.184	[-0.202, 0.569]	14 st, 168 eff	0.111	[-0.318, 0.540]	11 st, 119 eff	0.121	[-0.307, 0.549]	7 st, 44 eff
Lepidoptera	Richness	0.461	[0.315, 0.606]	5 st, 65 eff	0.528	[0.346, 0.709]	5 st, 44 eff			4 st, 21 eff
	Quantity	0.47	[0.266, 0.674]	8 st, 97 eff	0.408	[0.130, 0.685]	8 st, 78 eff			3 st, 19 eff
Butterflies	Richness			4 st, 39 eff			4 st, 28 eff			3 st, 11 eff
	Quantity			3 st, 50 eff			3 st, 40 eff			2 st, 10 eff
Moths	Richness			1 st, 26 eff			1 st, 16 eff			1 st, 10 eff
	Quantity			1 st, 25 eff			1 st, 16 eff			1 st, 9 eff
Hymenoptera	Richness			4 st, 47 eff			4 st, 31 eff			2 st, 16 eff
	Quantity	0.069	[-0.149, 0.287]	7 st, 92 eff	0.102	[-0.090, 0.294]	7 st, 76 eff			2 st, 16 eff
Bees	Richness	0.269	[0.174, 0.364]	5 st, 31 eff			4 st, 12 eff			4 st, 12 eff
	Quantity	0.216	[-0.312, 0.744]	8 st, 87 eff	0.184	[-0.188, 0.556]	6 st, 63 eff			3 st, 19 eff
Wasps	Richness			4 st, 47 eff			4 st, 31 eff			2 st, 16 eff
	Quantity			4 st, 67 eff			4 st, 51 eff			2 st, 16 eff
Hoverflies	Richness			3 st, 32 eff			3 st, 32 eff			
	Quantity	0.357	[-0.057, 0.771]	8 st, 76 eff	0.487	[0.078, 0.896]	7 st, 54 eff			4 st, 22 eff

Supporting Information Table S2. Meta-analyses (effect sizes presented in logarithmic Ratio of Means) for field-wise total observed richness (totSR) comparisons between agroforestry and monoculture controls. Models fitted with rma.mv, restricted maximum likelihood and random term = Study/Site when the number of applied studies equalized or exceeded 5 and the number of sites studied equalized or exceeded 10. CI = 95% confidence interval, st = studies, eff = effect sizes. Legend: **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture. Fainter (not bold) values represent not significant results ($P < 0.05$). The colors of the species groups appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Species group	<i>mean_{SA}</i>	<i>CI_{SA}</i>	<i>n_{SA}</i>	<i>mean_{SP}</i>	<i>CI_{SP}</i>	<i>n_{SP}</i>
Overall	0.207	[0.067, 0.346]	20 st, 287 eff	0.291	[0.059, 0.524]	12 st, 98 eff
Arthropods	0.195	[0.040, 0.351]	15 st, 237 eff	0.072	[-0.132, 0.276]	7 st, 45 eff
Aboveground invertebrates	0.303	[0.092, 0.514]	8 st, 71 eff	0.087	[-0.147, 0.321]	5 st, 38 eff
Soil-related invertebrates	-0.012	[-0.304, 0.280]	12 st, 210 eff	0.095	[-0.155, 0.345]	5 st, 30 eff
Autotrophs	0.705	[0.076, 1.335]	5 st, 52 eff			3 st, 17 eff
Lichens						
Natural enemies	-0.13	[-0.409, 0.149]	12 st, 226 eff	0.35	[0.060, 0.639]	10 st, 87 eff
Spiders	-0.332	[-0.775, 0.111]	5 st, 58 eff			4 st, 26 eff
Beetles	0.132	[-0.043, 0.307]	7 st, 140 eff			1 st, 4 eff
Ladybugs						1 st, 4 eff
Staphylinids			1 st, 5 eff			
Carabids	0.117	[-0.072, 0.305]	5 st, 130 eff			1 st, 4 eff
Ants						
Flying vertebrates			4 st, 37 eff	0.58	[0.094, 1.067]	5 st, 57 eff
Birds			3 st, 31 eff			3 st, 18 eff
Bats			1 st, 6 eff			2 st, 39 eff
Pest species	0.515	[0.178, 0.853]	11 st, 72 eff	-0.036	[-0.315, 0.243]	5 st, 24 eff
Gastropods			2 st, 7 eff			
Soil fauna	0.234	[0.084, 0.384]	9 st, 157 eff			2 st, 6 eff
Earthworms			1 st, 16 eff			1 st, 2 eff
Microbiota						
Centipedes			1 st, 1 eff			
Millipedes			3 st, 52 eff			
Woodlice			2 st, 50 eff			
Pollinators	0.475	[0.310, 0.639]	6 st, 58 eff			4 st, 21 eff
Lepidoptera			4 st, 42 eff			3 st, 19 eff
Butterflies			3 st, 27 eff			2 st, 10 eff
Moths			1 st, 15 eff			1 st, 9 eff
Hymenoptera			3 st, 29 eff			2 st, 16 eff
Bees			1 st, 5 eff			1 st, 2 eff
Wasps			3 st, 29 eff			2 st, 16 eff
Hoverflies			3 st, 17 eff			

Supporting Information Table S3. Meta-analyses (effect sizes presented in logarithmic Ratio of Means) for coefficient response of moderator Age (as a linear trend) to biodiversity richness (mean richness over plots), total richness (total richness across plots) and quantity (expressed in abundance, activity, biomass) metrics for comparisons between agroforestry and monoculture controls. Models fitted with rma.mv, restricted maximum likelihood and random term = Study/Site. CI = 95% confidence interval, st = studies, eff = effect sizes. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture. Fainter (not bold) values represent not significant results ($P < 0.05$). The colors of the species groups appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Species group	Metric	mean _{AF}	CI _{AF}	n _{AF}	mean _{SA}	CI _{SA}	n _{SA}	mean _{SP}	CI _{SP}	n _{SP}
Overall	Richness	-0.002	[-0.005, 0.002]	46 st, 638 eff	0.003	[-0.022, 0.008]	31 st, 479 eff	-0.007	[-0.015, 0.001]	19 st, 156 eff
	Quantity	0.229	[0.217, 0.241]	47 st, 660 eff	0.264	[0.253, 0.275]	35 st, 513 eff	-0.000	[-0.013, 0.013]	14 st, 141 eff
Overall	Richness									
	Quantity	0.229	[0.217, 0.241]	47 st, 660 eff						
Aboveground invertebrates	Total richness									
	Richness									
	Quantity				0.044	[0.033, 0.055]	19 st, 171 eff			
	Total richness									
Natural enemies	Richness	0.001	[-0.005, 0.007]	25 st, 469 eff						
	Quantity	0.026	[0.019, 0.033]	29 st, 404 eff						
	Total richness	-0.001	[-0.138, 0.134]	19 st, 318 eff						
Pollinators	Richness									
	Quantity	0.001	[-0.007, 0.010]	13 st, 162 eff						
	Total richness									

Supporting Information Table S4. Meta-analyses (effect sizes presented in logarithmic Ratio of Means) for coefficient response of moderator Age (as a log-transformed (ln) trend) to richness (mean richness over plots), total richness (total richness across plots) and quantity (expressed in abundance, acitivity, biomass) metrics for comparisons between agroforestry and monoculture controls. Models fitted with rma.mv, restricted maximum likelihood and random term = Study/Site. CI = 95% confidence interval, st = studies, eff = effect sizes. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture. Fainter (not bold) values represent not significant results (P < 0.05). The colors of the species groups appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Species group	Metric	mean _{AF}	CI _{AF}	n _{AF}	mean _{SA}	CI _{SA}	n _{SA}	mean _{SP}	CI _{SP}	n _{SP}
Overall	Richness	-0.036	[-0.097, 0.025]	46 st, 638 eff	0.005	[-0.063, 0.074]	31 st, 479 eff	-0.212	[-0.431, 0.006]	19 st, 156 eff
	Quantity	2.032	[1.923, 2.137]	47 st, 660 eff	2.257	[2.160, 2.354]	35 st, 513 eff	-0.159	[-0.529, 0.210]	14 st, 141 eff
Overall	Richness									
	Quantity	2.032	[1.923, 2.137]	47 st, 660 eff						
Aboveground invertebrates	Total richness									
	Richness									
	Quantity				0.750	[0.607, 0.894]	19 st, 171 eff			
Natural enemies	Total richness									
	Richness	-0.002	[-0.138, 0.134]	25 st, 469 eff						
	Quantity	0.524	[0.403, 0.643]	29 st, 404 eff						
Pollinators	Total richness	-0.021	[-0.188, 0.146]	19 st, 318 eff						
	Richness									
	Quantity	0.039	[-0.155, 0.232]	13 st, 162 eff						
	Total richness									

Supplementary methods Text S1: Dataset extraction protocol & studies assessed

Table 1. All criteria, along with their description and unit (if applicable), extracted per study in case it was reported. If not applicable, columns were left blank (NA, not a value) in the database.

Column	Explanation	Unit
Ref	In-text APA citation style as plain text (First author et al. YYYY)	
Title	Title of the case-study/publication	
Climate	Climate type of site-location (<i>Boreal/Alpine, Temperate, Mediterranean</i>)	
Country	Country of the site-location	
System	System for which the row applies: <i>Agroforestry = plots across an unspecified agroforestry system</i> <i>Silvoarable tree line = plots in a silvoarable tree line</i> <i>Silvoarable alley = plots in a silvoarable alley</i> <i>Silvoarable = plots across silvoarable system</i> <i>Silvopastoral = plots across silvopastoral system</i> <i>Silvopastoral alley = plots in a silvopastoral alley</i> <i>Food forest = plots across a food forest</i> <i>Forest grazing = plots across grazed forest</i> <i>Hedgerow = plots in a hedgerow</i> <i>Agroecosystem = plots in an unspecified agroecosystem</i> <i>Arable = plots in arable control</i> <i>Pasture = plots in pastoral control</i> <i>Forest = plots in forest control</i> <i>Orchard = plots in orchard control</i>	
Specif	Specifications with system (mostly management- or design-applied): e.g., tree line orientation, tree management, tilling management, ...	
Org/Conv	Organic (<i>Org</i>) or Conventional (<i>Conv</i>) farming applied	
Tree spec	Woody species in the study site	
Crop spec	Crop species for agricultural use in the plots (not applicable for pastoral sites)	
Metric	Biodiversity metric investigated: <i>ab = abundance/activity-density/biomass</i> <i>SR = richness indices (species-, family-, order-) on plot level</i> <i>totSR = richness indices (species-, family-, order-) for an entire agroforestry unit (field, tree line, ...)</i> <i>div = diversity indices (specified in Comments column)</i>	
Spec	The taxonomic species group investigated (as low as possible, more information on groups extracted in Supplementary Information Text S2)	
Means	Value for mean extracted for this group from the study (from text, figures, tables, appendices or raw data)	
SD	Standard deviation of mean for this group	
SE	If standard deviation of means was not given, we aimed for standard error for later conversion	
CI	If neither standard deviation of means nor standard error of means were given, we aimed for the mean of the confidence interval: $\frac{CI_{upper} - CI_{lower}}{2}$ for later conversion by assuming normal distribution	
n	Number of experiments carried out	
Crtl dist	Distance of a control area (arable or pastoral plot) to a tree row	<i>m</i>
Age	Age of an agroforestry system	<i>year</i>
Grazing dens	Grazing density of pastoral sites (categorized in high, medium, low or very low)	
Grazing spec	Species grazing on pastoral sites	
Sampling year	Year of sampling	<i>year</i>
Comments	Comments of clarification with data-extraction, could be referring to Figures, tables, diversity metrics, ...	
Loc region	Coordinates of the broader region where the research was carried out. This stays the same for fields located within 3km of each other	<i>decimal lat-lng</i>
Loc exact	Coordinates on plot/field-level if available	<i>decimal lat-lng</i>
Rawdata	Whether raw data on species level is being reported or available	
Strip width	Specification on the width of a tree strip	<i>m</i>

Alley width	Specification on the width of alleys in between tree strips. For silvopastoral systems often calculated as: $\sqrt{\frac{area}{tree\ density}}$	<i>m</i>
Tree h	Mean height of the trees at sampling time	<i>m</i>
Tree dbh	Mean dbh of trees at sampling time	<i>cm</i>

Per case-study, we selected the most detailed means (and their uncertainty, if given) for specified treatments (agroforestry) and controls (agriculture, set-asides, forest). These details were retrieved from main texts, appendices, tables, raw data or figures (with the aid of PlotDigitizer: <https://plotdigitizer.com/>). For case-studies only reporting boxplot results, without suitable appendices or model outputs, nor raw data availability, we estimated means and standard deviations assuming normal distributions as follows:

$$\mu = \frac{Min_{whisker} + Q1 + Median + Q3 + Max_{whisker}}{5} \quad \mu = mean$$

$$sd = \frac{IQR}{1.35} = \frac{Q3 - Q1}{1.35}$$

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Supplementary methods Text S2: Purification and discretization of the dataset

Step 1: Dataset cleaning

1. Calculating standard deviation (SD) from standard error (SE) or confidence interval (CI)

$$SD = SE\sqrt{n}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{n} \frac{CI}{1.96} \quad n > 60$$

$$SD = \sqrt{n} \frac{CI}{qt(0.95, n)} \quad n \leq 60$$

2. Species grouping based on taxonomy and functionality

Table 1: Species vector grouping. All groups in taxonomic grouping, functional group, taxon and subgroup are withheld in the final database in long format (meaning rows with 'Spec' categorized in more than one group are multiplied). Taxa indicated in grey are not included as specified group in the final dataset. The colors of the functional group names appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species.

Spec	Taxonomic grouping	Functional group	Taxon	Subgroup
Bacteria	Microbiota	Soil fauna		
Bats	Flying vertebrates	Natural enemies	Chiroptera	
Ladybugs	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Coleoptera	
Curculionids	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Coleoptera	
Chrysomelids	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Coleoptera	
Elator beetles	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Coleoptera	
Carabids	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna Natural enemies	Coleoptera	Carabids
Staphylinids	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna Natural enemies	Coleoptera	Staphylinids
Dung beetles	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Coleoptera	
Beetles	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Coleoptera	
Birds	Flying vertebrates	Natural enemies	Aves	
Cockroaches	Soil related invertebrates	Pest species	Blattaria	
Bugs	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Hemiptera	
Aphids	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Hemiptera	
Caterpillars	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Lepidoptera	
Butterflies	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Lepidoptera	Butterflies
Moths	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Lepidoptera	Moths
Lepidoptera	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Lepidoptera	
Caddisflies	Above-ground invertebrates		Trichoptera	
Centipedes	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna Natural enemies	Chilopoda	
Springtails	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Collembola	
Decapods	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna Natural enemies	Decapoda	
Earwigs	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna Natural enemies	Dermoptera	
Detritivores	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna		
Soil fauna	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna		
Flies	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators Pest species	Diptera	
Hoverflies	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Diptera	
Slender-legged flies	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Diptera	
Robber flies	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Diptera	

Dragonflies	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Odonata	
Earthworms	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Lumbricidae	
Mayflies	Above-ground invertebrates		Ephemeroptera	
Fungi	Microbiota	Soil fauna		
Gastropods	Soil related invertebrates	Pest species	Gastropoda	
Grasshoppers	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Orthoptera	
Harvestmen	Soil related invertebrates	Natural enemies	Opiliones	
Herbivores		Pest species		
Pest species		Pest species		
Plants		Autotrophs	Plantae	
		Pest species		
Herbs		Autotrophs	Plantae	
		Pest species		
Shrubs		Autotrophs	Plantae	
Trees		Autotrophs	Plantae	
Herpetofauna	Ground dwelling vertebrates	Natural enemies	Herpetofauna	
Small mammals	Ground dwelling vertebrates	Pest species	Small mammals	
Leeches	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Hirudinea	
		Natural enemies		
Ants	Soil related invertebrates	Natural enemies	Hymenoptera	<i>Ants</i>
Bees	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Hymenoptera	<i>Bees</i>
Wasps	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Hymenoptera	<i>Wasps</i>
		Natural enemies		
Hymenoptera	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators	Hymenoptera	
		Natural enemies		
Woodlice	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Isopoda	
Lacewings	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Neuroptera	
Thrips	Above-ground invertebrates	Pest species	Thysanoptera	
Fleas	Soil related invertebrates	Pest species	Siphonaptera	
Lichen		Autotrophs		<i>Lichen</i>
Megaloptera	Above-ground invertebrates	Natural enemies	Megaloptera	
Millipedes	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Diplopoda	
Mites	Soil related invertebrates	Natural enemies	Acari	
Mosses		Autotrophs	Bryophyta	
Nematodes	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Nematoda	
		Pest species		
Natural enemies		Natural enemies		
Parasites		Natural enemies		
Parasitoids		Natural enemies		
Predators		Natural enemies		
Pollinators	Above-ground invertebrates	Pollinators		
Pseudoscorpions	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Pseudoscorpiones	
Spiders	Soil related invertebrates	Natural enemies	Araneae	
Stoneflies	Above-ground invertebrates		Plecoptera	
Barkflies	Soil related invertebrates	Pest species	Psocoptera	
Silverfishes	Soil related invertebrates	Soil fauna	Zygentoma	

3. Total species richness allocation within metrics

Total species richness (totSR) is allocated to species richness metric rows with $n = 1$, as these rows present the absolute set of species found in one site, representing more information on less often occurring species for a plot.

4. Age & Alley width numeration and capping

Where 'Age' was assigned mature, we indicate this as being '60' as arbitrary value to ensure a numerical vector. We additionally capped all values with 60 as a maximum. Alley width was also capped at 60 meter since most effects are monitored in smaller scales.

5. System homogenization

We carried out following changes:

- Forest grazing → Silvopasture (Forest grazing is a silvopastoral practice in more forest-like conditions)
- Forest plantation → Forest (uniformization of forest control; specifications are mentioned in the ‘Specif’ column)

We also made several duplications of effect sizes for proper typology grouping:

- Agroforestry → contains additional information on: Silvopastoral, Silvoarable, Hedgerows, Silvoarable tree line, Silvoarable alley, Silvopastoral tree line, Silvopastoral alley
- Hedgerows → contains additional information on: Silvoarable tree line, Silvopastoral tree line

6. Crop type homogenization

Table 2: Handling different crop species and categorizing in different groups.

Crop type	Specific crops
Cereals	Barley, Wheat, Oats, Rye, Millet, Triticale
Corn	Maize
Mass-flowering crops	Alfalfa, Brassica, Buckwheat, Clover, Oilseed, Rapeseed, Soybean, Sunflower
Grass	Grass, Brome
Vegetables	Cabbage, Lettuce, Zucchini, Strawberries, Tomatoes, Peas, Beans, Carrots, Vetch
Orchard	Orchard, Vineyard
Ley	Ley

After this homogenization, we grouped the grass and ley group to ‘Grass/Ley’ and the mass flowering crop and vegetables group to ‘Vegetables/Mass flowering crops’.

7. Woody feature characterization

In the first phase, all woody species planted or present in the agroforestry element were noted in one column. Now, to process this data, we counted the number of genera (Tree_SR)¹ and categorized whether species were present forming either a shrub and/or tree layer. We also evaluated whether trees had a pollination need/service. We also categorized trees in functional types with the aim to establish a data column for tree typology (only applied when one typology was present in the agroforestry element). See Table 3 for categorization.

Table 3: Tree vector grouping based on typology and functioning.

Genus	Typology	Pollination service	Tree/Shrub
<i>Abies</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Acer</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Alnus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Betula</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Caragana</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Carpinus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Carya</i>	Other broadleaveds	Yes	Tree
<i>Castanea</i>	Nut-bearers		Tree
<i>Celtis</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Cistus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Cornus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub

¹ For case-studies not mentioning the exact species planted, but assigned a ‘mixed’ value, we awarded the highest SR recorded in the dataset. We additionally capped all numbers of 5 or higher to being maximum 5.

<i>Corylus</i>	Nut-bearers		Shrub
<i>Crataegus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Cupressus</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Cytisus</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Euonymus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Fagus</i>	Nut-bearers		Tree
<i>Fraxinus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Genista</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Gleditsia</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Hippocastanum</i>	Nut-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Hippophae</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Ilex</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Juglans</i>	Nut-bearers		Tree
<i>Larix</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Liriodendron</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Malus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Morus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Nothofagus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Shrub
<i>Olea</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Ostrya</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Paulownia</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Picea</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Pinus</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Platanus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Populus</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Prunus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Pseudotsuga</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Pyrus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Quercus</i>	Nut-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Retama</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Ribes</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Robinia</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Rosa</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Rubus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Salix</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Sambucus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Sorbus</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Thuja</i>	Conifers		Tree
<i>Tilia</i>	Flower-bearers	Yes	Tree
<i>Ulmus</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree
<i>Viburnum</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Vitis</i>	Fruit-bearers	Yes	Shrub
<i>Zelkova</i>	Other broadleaveds		Tree

8. Coordinates streamlining

Loc_{region} represents the study region for all studies assessed. Some studies are however carried out in the same regions, but when assessed separately, different coordinates might occur per region. We streamline this by clustering Loc_{region} in buffers of 3km.

We performed the same method for the exact locations (on field or plot level – if reported), but in buffers of 75m. After clustering, each unique value for Loc_{exact} was assigned a unique Site ID, when exact coordinates weren't known, a Site ID was derived from Loc_{region}². We also assigned Region IDs based on Loc_{region}. Simultaneously, also Study IDs were assigned to all separate studies.

9. Landscape compositional factors and soil typology

² Sites with no coordinate information at all were indexed separately per country

'Loc_exact' represents exact coordinates for the fields investigated (if given). For these coordinates we calculate compositional heterogeneity within a buffer of 1km, and extracted soil information for the exact coordinate. When 'loc_exact' could not be retrieved, we used the regional coordinates as estimation (presuming a rather continuous habitat and soil typology³), for which we applied a buffer of 3km. Soil data was extracted for the exact coordinate only.

For calculating compositional heterogeneity, we used the ESA Worldcover map of 2021 (<https://worldcover2021.esa.int/>; Zanaga et al., 2022), presuming continuity of landscape facets. This spatial feature offers map layers, based on satellite imagery, has a resolution of 10m and claims accuracy of more than 75%. We used function *reclassify* (to reclassify all classes to presence-absence matrices) and *extract* (to calculate the fraction of total pixels being classified as a specific class), both present in package raster (R. Hijmans, 2025). If needed (location coordinates were close to raster tile edges), tiles were merged beforehand using the *merge* function. We re-categorized the output in % tree-covered land, % shrubland, % grassland, % cropland, % open water, % built-up land and % other land. As proxy for seminatural (and wooded) land in the area, we summed the % tree-covered land and % shrubland and as a proxy for open land, we summed % grassland and % cropland. These metrics represent then landscape composition. Additionally, landscape shannon diversity was calculated using the composition fractions of tree-covered land, shrubland, cropland, grassland, built-up land, open water and other ecosystems.

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n fraction_i * \ln(fraction_i)$$

For extracting soil typology, we used SoilGrids™ (<https://soilgrids.org/>; Hengl et al., 2017). This spatial feature offers map layers, based on modelling across global layers and input data of a database of a quarter million soil cores, with resolution of 250m. Soil properties can be requested for different depths. We extracted data on coarse material fraction, clay fraction, sand fraction and silt fraction for three depths (0-5cm, 5-15cm and 15-30cm). With weighted means, we calculated the share of each fraction in the overall 0-30cm layer. We used these fractions to catalogize soils with the USDA Soil Texture Triangle (**Figure 1**; Groenendyk et al., 2015; Moreno-Maroto & Alonso-Azcárate, 2022), grouping further as follows: clay (clay, silty clay, sandy clay, silty clay loam, sandy clay loam), loam (silt, silt loam, loam) and sand (sand, loamy sand, sandy loam).

³ This is often valid for large-scale silvopastoral agroforestry systems, for which the majority of studies only represent regional coordinates.

Figure 1. USDA Soil Texture Triangle (Groenendyk et al., 2015).

Step 2: long-format dataframe to wide-format dataframe

With the full long-format database created, we have to convert it to a wide-format for making comparisons between study-ID-plot-types (i.e., the field-level or plot-level research carried out per study).

A first conceptual purification performed is summarizing taxonomic outputs per study and site for the appropriate groups indicated. This ensures no overdilution effects are present towards research performing studies with multiple taxonomic outputs.

$$mean_{group} = \sum_{i=1}^n mean_{taxon}$$

$$sd_{group} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n sd_{taxon}^2}$$

The following matching rules are applied:

- Matches for: (study, region, crop group, organic/conventional farming, sampling year, metric, taxonomic group from raw set).
 - Crop group and organic/conventional farming are only applied when comparing to agricultural controls.
 - Grazing species is only applied in pastoral systems.
 - When metric represents a diversity metric, also column 'Comments' is used (contains more detail on diversity metric)
- All moderator data is from the agroforestry system line, except for:
 - Crop group (when empty – comparing with hedgerows)
 - Organic/conventional farming (when empty – comparing with hedgerows)

The following matches are constructed:

- Silvoarable tree line
 - Silvoarable alley
 - Field margin
 - Arable
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Silvoarable alley
 - Arable
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Silvoarable
 - Arable
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Silvopastoral tree line
 - Silvoarable alley
 - Field margin
 - Pasture
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Silvopastoral alley
 - Pasture
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Silvopastoral
 - Silvopastoral alley
 - Pasture
 - Forest
 - Orchard
- Hedgerows
 - Field margin
 - Forest
 - Orchard
 - Arable
 - Pasture
- Agroforestry
 - Agroecosystem
 - Forest
 - Orchard

Silvoarable tree line and silvoarable alley were grouped under agroforestry type and silvopastoral tree line and silvopastoral alley were grouped integrated in the silvopastoral type in a new column AF_{type} . The plot typologies were additionally stocked into $AF_{plottyp}$.

Processing of 0-values:

When a certain group had zero-outputs in a specific line (absence), Ratio of Means⁴ effect sizes could not be calculated. Therefore, some adjustments were needed. Lines in which both treatment and control had zero-outputs were removed as well as diversity metrics (not abundance or species richness) where a zero-output occurred in either the treatment or control. For abundance and species richness (where zero-outputs do have a meaningful ecological interpretation if compared to a non-zero output), we added a small +1 correction to all records (ensuring comparability) to allow calculation of log-transformed response ratios.

Imputing standard deviation when none was given:

Not all of the retrieved studies reported uncertainty metrics. If a study didn't report a standard deviation, standard error or confidence interval for a certain output, we assumed its variability matches the typical proportional variability (CV) observed for the corresponding agroforestry type and control.

⁴ Note that for other effect sizes 0-values might be not problematic

Step 3: Effect size calculation

We have to calculate particular effect sizes based on the means and standard deviations of treatment and control groups. For this purpose, we used the *escalc* function from the R-package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010). We chose to use method 'ROM', reflecting Ratio of Means. For each observation, the effect size was computed as:

$$ROM = \ln\left(\frac{\mu_{Treatment}}{\mu_{Control}}\right) \quad \mu = mean$$

While the sampling variance was computed as:

$$Var_{ROM} = \frac{sd_{Treatment}^2}{n_{Treatment} * \mu_{Treatment}^2} + \frac{sd_{Control}^2}{n_{Control} * \mu_{Control}^2}$$

Supplementary methods Text S3: Variable exploration & selection

Step 1: Variable exploration

For a first step of exploration, we used per agroforestry type in consideration the dataset representing overall biodiversity. This avoided skew due to studies reporting multiple biodiversity groups. **Table 1** gives an overview per agroforestry type of all 28 variables considered and their distributions.

Table 1. Variable exploration. The first plot displays effect size sensitivity for all agroforestry types, displayed with `geom_smooth` (method `rlm`, with `MASS` package, and method `loess`, with `span 1` and without standard error indication) for numeric variables and with violin distributions for discrete variables. The second plot shows effect size density along continuous variables or bar counts for discrete variables. Legend: **blue** = agroforestry-general, **brown** = silvoarable, **green** = silvopasture.

Climate

Climate

Country

Country

Fraction of cropland area (%)

cropfrac

Crop type

Cropgroup

Fraction of woody vegetation area (%)

forestshrubfrac

Fraction of open habitat area (%)

grasscropfrac

Grazing density

grazing_dens

Grazing species

grazing_spec

Landscape diversity

landscape_shannon

Organic or conventional management

Org.Conv

Region ID

Region_ID

Sampling year

Sampling_year

Presence of shrub layer

Shrub_layer

Site ID

Site_ID

Rocky presence in soil

Soil_rocks

Soil type

Soil_type

Strip width

Strip_width

Study ID

Study_ID

Tree type

Tree.cat

Tree diameter

Tree.diameter

Tree height

Tree.height

Pollination potential of woody feature

Tree.pol

Presence of tree layer

Tree.layer

Woody richness

TreesR

Figure 1. Effect size overlap among variables and absolute amount through the dataset.

In a next step, we explored variables⁵ by performing non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) with Gower distance (able to cope with logical, continuous and categorical variables and scaling those on a zero to one scale) with R-packages vegan and cluster (**Figure 2**). Here we did not separate biodiversity metrics specifically as we want an overview of the overall dataset patterns.

Figure 2. Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) with Gower distance.

⁵ Variables Tree diameter and Tree height were excluded as overlap with other moderators was dramatically low (Figure 1).

In a final explorative step, we calculated the actual correlations between our continuous variables (**Figure 3**). Again, we did not separate biodiversity metrics. We used package corrplot (Wei & Simko, 2024) for this purpose after calculating the correlation matrix.

Figure 3. Correlations of continuous variables, calculated with function findCorrelation from package caret and visualized with corrplot from the corrplot package.

Step 2: Moderator selection

As of now, our complete dataset still contains 28 variables (apart from taxonomic group, biodiversity metric, agroforestry type and baseline system). Some of these moderators correspond with random influences in the data (i.e., study ID, Region ID, Site ID, country, sampling year), while others potentially correspond as fixed variables influencing biodiversity changes. Therefore, we have to carry out well-considered moderator selection.

In terms of random variables, we integrated 'Study ID' as an important random intercept, incorporating implicit information on sampling year and study design. We chose to nest 'Site ID' in 'Study ID' to correspond for site differences within a single study. To test fixed variables, we constructed univariate *rma.mv* (package *metafor* (Viechtbauer, 2010)) models with method Maximum Likelihood (ML) and the random factors discussed above and tested species richness and abundance models for overall biodiversity across the agroforestry types used in the manuscript (i.e., agroforestry in general, silvoarable and silvopastoral) in comparison with non-agroforestry agricultural land. This model was compared to the respective null-model (with the same dataset) with a likelihood ratio test (function *anova*). Additionally, the same model was fitted with method Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) to get more stable coefficient estimates for the moderator considered and tested significance of this coefficient with an omnibus test.

For the final decision about incorporation or neglectance of potential moderators, we considered (i) variable correlations (**Figure 3**), (ii) meta-analysis model outputs and (iii) ecological functioning in ecosystems. All of this is given in **Table 2**.

$$\begin{aligned} effectsize_{ij} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 * Moderator + u_i + r_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \\ effectsize_{ij} &= \beta_0 + u_i + r_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\sim N(0, \tau^2) && \text{between study random intercept} \\ r_{ij} &\sim N(0, \sigma^2) && \text{within study random intercept} \\ \varepsilon_{ij} &\sim N(0, variance_{ij}) && \text{known sampling error} \\ & && i \quad \text{study}; j \quad \text{effect size} \end{aligned}$$

Table 2. Moderator selection and statistical understanding of moderator functioning. (Red = exclusion, Green = inclusion). Statistical evidence here is based on a likelihood ratio test (anova) between a null-model and the univariate model fitted on the same dataset with method Maximum Likelihood (P_{LRT}) and based on the omnibus test for the moderator applied in a model with method Restricted Maximum Likelihood (P_{omn}). (AF = agroforestry overall, SA = Silvoarable, SP = Silvopastoral, SR = species richness, ab = abundance). Fainter (not bold) values represent not significant results (P < 0.05).

Moderator and specifications	Reasoning	Statistical evidence															
Agroforestry plot type	This variable does not provide ecological meaning of the system towards users, but contains information of the spatial plot characterization. In this sense, it does explain a lot of variation (for instance differences between a crop alley plot and a treeline). Due to the limited numbers of states, we used it as a fixed effect, since opting to use it as a random effect is statistically a poor choice (Fernández-Castilla et al., 2020).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.00 0.88</td> <td>0.00 0.55</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.00 0.35</td> <td>0.00 0.21</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.90 0.92</td> <td>0.00 0.34</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.00 0.88	0.00 0.55	SA	0.00 0.35	0.00 0.21	SP	0.90 0.92	0.00 0.34
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.00 0.88	0.00 0.55															
SA	0.00 0.35	0.00 0.21															
SP	0.90 0.92	0.00 0.34															
Age (y)	With the woody component of an agroforestry system growing older, the effects should get more pronounced since the effects on microclimate and habitat generated increase (Edo et al., 2025; Kletty et al., 2023). In contrary, species related to open landscape might move away from these structural features.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.24 0.23</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.91 0.93</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.07 0.07</td> <td>0.96 0.97</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.24 0.23	0.00 0.00	SA	0.91 0.93	0.00 0.00	SP	0.07 0.07	0.96 0.97
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.24 0.23	0.00 0.00															
SA	0.91 0.93	0.00 0.00															
SP	0.07 0.07	0.96 0.97															
Alley width/Tree density (m)	Tree density affects the amount of new structural habitat created (Kletty et al., 2023).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.03 0.03</td> <td>0.02 0.02</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.98 0.98</td> <td>0.73 0.73</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.01 0.01</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.03 0.03	0.02 0.02	SA	0.98 0.98	0.73 0.73	SP	0.00 0.00	0.01 0.01
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.03 0.03	0.02 0.02															
SA	0.98 0.98	0.73 0.73															
SP	0.00 0.00	0.01 0.01															
Fraction of builtup area (%)	Landscape likely inflicts mitigating effects (Kletty et al., 2023). Slight correlation (64%) with Shannon landscape diversity, which is in terms of landscape influence better suited.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.17 0.17</td> <td>0.86 0.86</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.03 0.03</td> <td>0.69 0.69</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.79 0.79</td> <td>0.53 0.54</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.17 0.17	0.86 0.86	SA	0.03 0.03	0.69 0.69	SP	0.79 0.79	0.53 0.54
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.17 0.17	0.86 0.86															
SA	0.03 0.03	0.69 0.69															
SP	0.79 0.79	0.53 0.54															
Climate	Different climate zones are likely to behave differently and species compositions are different, potentially affecting generated effects (García de León et al., 2021; Kletty et al., 2023; Torralba et al., 2016).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.05 0.05</td> <td>0.01 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.67 0.67</td> <td>0.23 0.23</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.03 0.02</td> <td>0.01 0.00</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.05 0.05	0.01 0.00	SA	0.67 0.67	0.23 0.23	SP	0.03 0.02	0.01 0.00
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.05 0.05	0.01 0.00															
SA	0.67 0.67	0.23 0.23															
SP	0.03 0.02	0.01 0.00															
Fraction of cropland area (%)	Landscape likely inflicts mitigating effects (Kletty et al., 2023). Slight correlation (62%) with fraction of woody habitat, which relates better to the agroforestry proxy.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.01 0.01</td> <td>0.07 0.07</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.01 0.01</td> <td>0.17 0.17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.59 0.60</td> <td>0.48 0.48</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.01 0.01	0.07 0.07	SA	0.01 0.01	0.17 0.17	SP	0.59 0.60	0.48 0.48
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.01 0.01	0.07 0.07															
SA	0.01 0.01	0.17 0.17															
SP	0.59 0.60	0.48 0.48															
Crop type	Only relevant for silvoarable sites. The crops grown at fields do inflict an own community of weeds, pest species and natural enemies. As such, the presence of a certain crop can influence biodiversity gains as well (Kletty et al., 2023).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF			SA	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00	SP		
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SA	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00															
SP																	

<p>Fraction of woody vegetation area (%)</p>	<p>Information on landscape composition, relating to the woody component of agroforestry. Landscape likely inflicts mitigating effects (Kletty et al., 2023). This is an understudied area in agroforestry systems, but there is already evidence found for mitigation effects in other agri-environmental measures (Batáry et al., 2011; Marja et al., 2019, 2024; Sánchez et al., 2022).</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.12 0.12</td> <td>0.04 0.04</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.22 0.22</td> <td>0.07 0.07</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.22 0.22</td> <td>0.36 0.37</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.12 0.12	0.04 0.04	SA	0.22 0.22	0.07 0.07	SP	0.22 0.22	0.36 0.37
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF	0.12 0.12	0.04 0.04															
SA	0.22 0.22	0.07 0.07															
SP	0.22 0.22	0.36 0.37															
<p>Fraction of open habitat area (%)</p>	<p>Landscape likely inflicts mitigating effects (Kletty et al., 2023). Highly correlated (91%) with fraction of woody habitat, which relates better to the woody component of agroforestry.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.08 0.08</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.03 0.03</td> <td>0.06 0.06</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.39 0.38</td> <td>0.02 0.02</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.08 0.08	0.00 0.00	SA	0.03 0.03	0.06 0.06	SP	0.39 0.38	0.02 0.02
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF	0.08 0.08	0.00 0.00															
SA	0.03 0.03	0.06 0.06															
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<p>Grazing density</p>	<p>Only relevant for silvopastoral sites. The density of grazers affects disturbance in the field and impacts floral diversity by trampling or grazing and related communities.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.78 0.79</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF			SA			SP	0.00 0.00	0.78 0.79
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
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<p>Grazing species</p>	<p>This data vector has many levels that overlap with each other and are thus not feasible to integrate as of yet, there could be a benefit to split this column in multiple presence-absence columns for grazers.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.98 0.99</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF			SA			SP	0.98 0.99	0.00 0.00
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF																	
SA																	
SP	0.98 0.99	0.00 0.00															
<p>Landscape diversity</p>	<p>Information on landscape diversity. Landscape likely inflicts mitigating effects (Kletty et al., 2023). This is an understudied area in agroforestry systems, but there is already evidence found for mitigation effects in other agri-environmental measures (Batáry et al., 2011; Marja et al., 2019, 2024; Sánchez et al., 2022).</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.21 0.21</td> <td>0.84 0.84</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.01 0.01</td> <td>0.45 0.45</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.54 0.56</td> <td>0.51 0.51</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.21 0.21	0.84 0.84	SA	0.01 0.01	0.45 0.45	SP	0.54 0.56	0.51 0.51
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF	0.21 0.21	0.84 0.84															
SA	0.01 0.01	0.45 0.45															
SP	0.54 0.56	0.51 0.51															
<p>Organic or conventional management</p>	<p>Organic agriculture has already been proven to improve biodiversity (Bengtsson et al., 2005; Lichtenberg et al., 2017; Tuck et al., 2014). Potential mitigation effects can play a role here (Kletty et al., 2023).</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.87 0.87</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF			SA	0.00 0.00	0.87 0.87	SP		
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF																	
SA	0.00 0.00	0.87 0.87															
SP																	
<p>Presence of shrub layer</p>	<p>The presence (or absence) of a shrub layer provides additional information on the vertical structure of a woody feature in agroforestry context. It represents an additional vegetation layer with added habitat and sheltering opportunities. Woody feature structure might mitigate biodiversity effects (Kletty et al., 2023).</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.08 0.08</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.89 0.89</td> <td>0.15 0.15</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.51 0.52</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.00 0.00	0.08 0.08	SA	0.89 0.89	0.15 0.15	SP	0.00 0.00	0.51 0.52
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF	0.00 0.00	0.08 0.08															
SA	0.89 0.89	0.15 0.15															
SP	0.00 0.00	0.51 0.52															
<p>Rocky presence in soil</p>	<p>The ecological relevance for biodiversity outputs in agroforestry systems is rather low. None of the univariate models show significant influences.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.80 0.80</td> <td>0.78 0.78</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.65 0.63</td> <td>0.35 0.35</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.69 0.66</td> <td>0.74 0.75</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.80 0.80	0.78 0.78	SA	0.65 0.63	0.35 0.35	SP	0.69 0.66	0.74 0.75
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF	0.80 0.80	0.78 0.78															
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SP	0.69 0.66	0.74 0.75															
<p>Soil type</p>	<p>Soil types inflict responses on soil fauna communities and plant communities, potentially mitigating agroforestry implementation responses for these groups (Kletty et al., 2023). However, none of the univariate models show any significant influences.</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.86 0.85</td> <td>0.90 0.90</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.47 0.48</td> <td>0.87 0.87</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.17 0.15</td> <td>0.41 0.31</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF	0.86 0.85	0.90 0.90	SA	0.47 0.48	0.87 0.87	SP	0.17 0.15	0.41 0.31
	SR	ab															
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SA	0.47 0.48	0.87 0.87															
SP	0.17 0.15	0.41 0.31															
<p>Strip width</p>	<p>Wider strips comprise more habitat for native biodiversity, inflicting potential effects (Kletty et al., 2023). This information is present in a limited amount of effect sizes and is not very diverse. This metric might however be more relevant when looking at hedgerow</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{Omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.85 0.85</td> <td>0.90 0.90</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	AF			SA	0.85 0.85	0.90 0.90	SP		
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}	P _{LRT} P _{Omn}															
AF																	
SA	0.85 0.85	0.90 0.90															
SP																	

	responses (where tree strip widths might be more variable). None of the univariate models show any significant influences.																
Tree type	Only present in 60-65% of the dataset, this data vector has many levels that overlap with each other and are thus not feasible to integrate as of yet, there could be a benefit to split this column in multiple presence-absence columns for tree types. It could be expected that tree species mitigate biodiversity responses (Kletty et al., 2023).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.71 0.71</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.00 0.00	0.71 0.71	SA	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00	SP	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.00 0.00	0.71 0.71															
SA	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00															
SP	0.00 0.00	0.00 0.00															
Tree diameter	Only present in 40-55% of the dataset, which would lead to data dilution, however not clear for the correlations, conceptually there should be a link with Age. Additionally, none of the univariate models show any significant influences.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.52 0.51</td> <td>0.72 0.73</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.66 0.66</td> <td>0.72 0.72</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.61 0.61</td> <td>0.85 0.83</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.52 0.51	0.72 0.73	SA	0.66 0.66	0.72 0.72	SP	0.61 0.61	0.85 0.83
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.52 0.51	0.72 0.73															
SA	0.66 0.66	0.72 0.72															
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Tree height	Only present in 40-55% of the dataset, which would lead to data dilution, however not clear for the correlations, conceptually there should be a link with Age. Additionally, none of the univariate models show any significant influences.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.44 0.45</td> <td>0.78 0.79</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.67 0.67</td> <td>0.86 0.85</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.17 0.21</td> <td>0.45 0.46</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.44 0.45	0.78 0.79	SA	0.67 0.67	0.86 0.85	SP	0.17 0.21	0.45 0.46
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.44 0.45	0.78 0.79															
SA	0.67 0.67	0.86 0.85															
SP	0.17 0.21	0.45 0.46															
Pollination potential of woody feature	Ecological trait of woody feature describing whether the feature offers resources to pollinating animals. Some of the univariate models show significant influences.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.34 0.34</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.06 0.06</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.69 0.65</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.00 0.00	0.34 0.34	SA	0.00 0.00	0.06 0.06	SP	0.00 0.00	0.69 0.65
	SR	ab															
	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}															
AF	0.00 0.00	0.34 0.34															
SA	0.00 0.00	0.06 0.06															
SP	0.00 0.00	0.69 0.65															
Presence of tree layer	Almost everywhere there are tree layer species present, so too little data to incorporate the FALSE-aspect, but this information presents effects on woody feature structure (Kletty et al., 2023).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.97 0.97</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.01 0.01</td> <td>0.47 0.44</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.80 0.82</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.00 0.00	0.97 0.97	SA	0.01 0.01	0.47 0.44	SP	0.00 0.00	0.80 0.82
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AF	0.00 0.00	0.97 0.97															
SA	0.01 0.01	0.47 0.44															
SP	0.00 0.00	0.80 0.82															
Woody richness	The number of woody genera present in the agroforestry element can appoint for structural and habitat differentiation of the element and therefor generate mitigation effects (Kletty et al., 2023).	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>SR</th> <th>ab</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> <th>P_{LRT} P_{omn}</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>AF</td> <td>0.02 0.02</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SA</td> <td>0.02 0.02</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SP</td> <td>0.00 0.00</td> <td>0.07 0.05</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		SR	ab		P _{LRT} P _{omn}	P _{LRT} P _{omn}	AF	0.02 0.02	0.00 0.00	SA	0.02 0.02	0.00 0.00	SP	0.00 0.00	0.07 0.05
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AF	0.02 0.02	0.00 0.00															
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SP	0.00 0.00	0.07 0.05															

Step 3: Continuous variable transformations

For continuous variables Alley.width, Age, forestshrub_frac and landscape_shannon we applied potential data transformations to account for non-linearity. We considered the following options:

- exp: e^x
- expmin: e^{-x}
- linear: x
- log: $\log(x)$
- minexpmin: $-e^{-x}$
- minlog: $-\log(x)$
- reversed: $\frac{1}{1+x}$
- reversedexp: $\frac{1}{1+e^x}$
- sqrt: \sqrt{x}

Since all mutual variations of data transformations are tested upon selecting the best performing model. Only two additional transformations are selected per variable (besides the linear trend). For this we chose the two best approaches when fitting all eight transformations in a univariate model like it was applied in Step 3.

forestshrub_frac transformations

landscape_shannon transformations

Figure 4. Transformations considered and retained (not shadowed) for model fitting. Blue lines represent trends when having positive coefficients, red lines represent trends when having negative coefficients.

Supplementary methods Text S4: Data handling

All data were analyzed and visualized with R (R Core Team, 2023) and PowerPoint, with packages dplyr (Wickham, François, et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, et al., 2023), forcats (Wickham, 2023a), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggrepel (Slowikowski, 2023), vegan (Oksanen et al., 2022), metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010), stringr (Wickham, 2025), car (Fox & Weisberg, 2019), caret (Kuhn, 2022), MASS (Venables & Ripley, 2002), purr (Wickham & Henry, 2025), tibble (Müller & Wickham, 2025), ggpattern (FC et al., 2022), gridExtra (Auguie, 2017), corrplot (Wei & Simko, 2024) and lme4 (Bates et al., 2015).

For the landscape analyses, we made use of additional packages sf (Pebesma, 2018; Pebesma & Bivand, 2023), terra (R. J. Hijmans, 2025), raster, sp (Pebesma, 2018), rgdal (Bivand et al., 2023), rgeos (Bivand & Rundel, 2023), maptools (Bivand & Lewin-Koh, 2023) and raster (R. Hijmans, 2025).

For soil information extraction, we made use of additional packages jsonlite (Ooms, 2014) and httr (Wickham, 2023b).

The tool interface was built with packages shinyjs (Attali, 2021) and shiny (Chang et al., 2025) and was published with package rsconnect (Atkins et al., 2025).

Phylopic.org authorship:

<i>Acharia stimulea</i> :	Richard Harris – 12/09/2021 – PDM 1.0
<i>Arcyptera fusca</i> :	Pascal Abel – 21/06/2025 – PDM 1.0
<i>Diapria conica</i> :	Kendrick Fowler – 14/02/2023 – PDM 1.0
<i>Cyphophthalmi</i> :	Markus Friedrich – 14/11/2024 – PDM 1.0
<i>Neoponera villosa</i> :	T. Michael Keeseey – 09/05/2018 – PDM 1.0
<i>Thalassia testudinum</i> :	T. Michael Keeseey – 13/11/2022 – PDM 1.0
Araneae:	T. Michael Keeseey – 06/10/2022 – CC0 1.0
Pseudoscorpiones:	T. Michael Keeseey – 06/10/2022 – CC0 1.0
<i>Cupido comyntas</i> :	Andy Wilson – 01/03/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Luperina Testacea</i> :	Andy Wilson – 28/03/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Cirsium discolor</i> :	Andy Wilson – 22/02/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Toxomerus politus</i> :	Andy Wilson – 22/02/2022 – CC0 1.0
<i>Lycorma delicatula</i> :	Andy Wilson – 01/03/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Passer domesticus</i> :	Andy Wilson – 21/02/2022 – CC0 1.0
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<i>Monochamus galloprovincialis</i> :	David Pires – 08/10/2022 – CC0 1.0
Gracillariidae:	Kanako Bessho-Uehara – 13/10/2021 – CC0 1.0
<i>Smycronyx</i> :	Kanako Bessho-Uehara – 27/05/2020 – CC0 1.0
<i>Bombus terrestris</i> :	Ferran Sayol – 14/07/2020 – CC0 1.0
<i>Athene noctua</i> :	Ferran Sayol – 04/06/2018 – CC0 1.0
<i>Lasioglossum calceatum</i> :	Ferran Sayol – 14/07/2020 – CC0 1.0
<i>Oniscus asellus</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 01/07/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Koelreuteria paniculata</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 21/06/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Vinca minor</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 09/07/2023 – CC0 1.0
Thysanoptera:	Guillaume Dera – 09/06/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Arion rufus</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 10/06/2023 – CC0 1.0

<i>Scolopendra gigantea</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 10/06/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Acheta domestica</i> :	Guillaume Dera – 09/06/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Corynorhinus townsendii</i> :	Yan Wong – 10/03/2025 – CC0 1.0
<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i> :	Carlo De Rito – 16/03/2023 – CC0 1.0
Leotiomyces:	Levi Simons – 22/01/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Saprospira</i> :	Levi Simons – 12/01/2023 – CC0 1.0
<i>Laccaria</i> :	Riccardo Percudani – 25/03/2022 – CC0 1.0
<i>Maratus speciosus</i> :	Kamil S. Jaron – 29/11/2022 – CC0 1.0
<i>Orchesella cincta</i> :	Kamil S. Jaron – 29/01/2020 – CC0 1.0
<i>Allacma fusca</i> :	Kamil S. Jaron – 28/09/2021 – CC0 1.0
Volutidae:	MBARI and FathomVerse – 18/07/2024 – CC0 1.0
<i>Podarcis erhardii</i> :	Alex Slavenko – 04/11/2024 – CC0 1.0
<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i> :	Margot Michaud – 03/04/2021 – CC0 1.0
<i>Nezara viridula</i> :	Darrin Schultz – 01/10/2025 – CC0 1.0
<i>Erebia</i> :	Mattia Menchetti – 18/02/2016 – CC0 1.0
Julida:	Gemma Martínez-Redondo – 05/10/2022 – CC0 1.0
<i>Leiopelma archeyi</i> :	Jose Carlos Arenas-Monfroy – 22/01/2023 – CC0 1.0
Asilidae:	Aleksandra Bliznina – 25/07/2025 – CC0 1.0